

LIST OF AMPHIBIANS OF BRAZIL

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Resumo

Atualizamos a lista de anfíbios do Brasil com base exclusivamente em evidências publicadas em literatura revisada por pares até Março de 2026. O trabalho incorpora novas descrições, mudanças taxonômicas, sinônimas, revalidações e registros confirmados, resultando na remoção de 41 espécies e na adição de 104 táxons. A fauna nacional passa a compreender 1251 espécies válidas, incluindo 1206 anuros, 40 cecílias e cinco salamandras. Assim, a lista fornece uma referência padronizada para estudos de sistemática, biogeografia, conservação e avaliações oficiais de risco.

Palavras-chave

Anura; Caudata; Diversidade; Gymnophiona.

ABSTRACT

We updated the list of Brazilian amphibians based exclusively on evidence published in peer-reviewed literature up to March 2026. This work incorporates new species descriptions, taxonomic changes, synonymizations, revalidations, and confirmed distribution records, resulting in the removal of 41 species and the addition of 104 taxa. The national fauna now comprises 1251 valid species, including 1206 anurans, 40 caecilians, and five salamanders. This updated list provides a standardized reference for studies in systematics, biogeography, conservation, and official risk assessments.

Keywords

Anura; Caudata; Diversity; Gymnophiona.

The most recent published list of Brazilian amphibians was compiled by Segalla et al. (2021), reporting 1188 species: 1144 anurans, 39 caecilians, and five salamanders. Accordingly, Brazil consistently holds the title of the country with the highest amphibian species richness in the world, followed by other South American countries such as Colombia (861 spp.), Ecuador (703 spp.), and Peru (682 spp.; Frost, 2025). In addition, there has been a growing trend in publications focused on amphibian diversity in Brazil and worldwide, with Brazil recognized as one of the countries with the greatest potential for the discovery of new species (Moura & Jetz, 2021). Several hypotheses have been proposed to explain the country's high amphibian richness, including its vast territorial extension, its location within the Neotropical region, as well as the diversity of ecoregions and complex topography (e.g. Toledo & Batista, 2012; Toledo et al., 2014; Moura et al., 2016). Since the publication of Segalla et al. (2021), several important studies have contributed to improving our knowledge of species diversity in Brazil (as detailed in subsequent sections), highlighting the need for an updated version of the national list. The species list provided here includes all currently recognized amphibian species known to occur within the political boundaries of Brazil as of 12 March 2026. For this compilation, we relied exclusively on evidence available in the peer-reviewed scientific literature. Suprageneric classification follows Frost (2025).

As detailed in the following sections, we propose the removal of 41 species and the addition of 104 species to the list, including 75 recently described species and 29 added for other taxonomic revisions or new distributional evidence. No changes were observed in the composition of salamanders, which continue to comprise five species within a single family and genus. In contrast, the number of anuran species has increased to 1206, distributed across 23 families and 111 genera, while caecilians now comprise 40 species belonging to four families and 13 genera. As a result, the known amphibian fauna of Brazil now comprises a total of 1251 species. Among these, two species, *Aquarana catesbeiana* and *Eleutherodactylus johnstonei*, are exotic, introduced, and invasive. Although a recent record reports an individual of *Kaloula pulchra* in the municipality

of Campo Formoso, Bahia (Máximo et al., 2021), we did not include this species in the current list, as there is no evidence of a population establishment in Brazil.

A) Genus-level changes since the last list:

- ***Allobates/Dryadobates*** – *Dryadobates* was erected by Grant et al. (2025) to accommodate Atlantic Forest species previously assigned to *Allobates*.

- ***Rhaebo/Adhaerobufo*** – *Adhaerobufo* was erected by Dias et al. (2024) to accommodate *Rhaebo nasicus* and *R. ceratophrys*.

- ***Caligophryne*** – Recently described genus and family (Caligophrynidae) by Fouquet et al. (2024a)

- ***Noblella/Phyllonastes*** – *Phyllonastes* was resurrected by von May et al. (2024) and Ortega et al. (2025) to accommodate species of the northern *Noblella* clade, while *Noblella sensu stricto* remains restricted to the southern clade.

- ***Lysapsus/Pseudis*** – *Lysapsus* was synonymized with *Pseudis* by Caballero-Gini et al. (2024).

- ***Scinax/Ololygon/Julianus*** – Duellman et al. (2016) divided *Scinax* into *Scinax*, *Ololygon*, and *Julianus*. This arrangement was confirmed by Araújo-Vieira et al. (2023).

- ***Megaelosia/Phantasmarana*** – *Phantasmarana* was erected by Vittorazzi et al. (2021) to resolve the paraphyly of *Megaelosia*.

- ***Relictocleis/Chiasmocleis*** – *Relictocleis* was elevated to genus level by Segalla et al. (2021), but following the most recent usage (Fouquet et al., 2022a; Frost, 2025), we list the species as *Chiasmocleis*.

- ***Neblinaphryne*** – Recently described genus and family (Neblinaphrynidae) by Fouquet et al. (2024a).

B) Species removed from the list published by Segalla et al. (2021):

Brachycephalidae

- ***Brachycephalus atelopoide*** – Bornschein et al. (2021) discussed the diagnosis and identity of *B. atelopoide* and concluded that

the best working solution might be to follow Cochran's (1955) proposal to place *B. atelopoide* in the synonymy of *B. ephippium*. We follow Bornschein et al. (2021) to avoid inflating the Brazilian species richness.

Bufonidae

•*Melanophryniscus dorsalis* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Melanophryniscus formosus* (Langone & Lavilla, 2024).

•*Rhaebo ecuadorensis* – The occurrence of the species in Brazil was proposed by Mueses-Cisneros et al. (2012) based on a subadult *Rhaebo* (32.2 mm SVL) cited by Lötters et al. (2000) that lacked both a preorbital ridge and ventral white spotting. Mueses-Cisneros et al. (2012) inferred that this specimen, reportedly from the “Brazilian central Amazon” (not “central Brazil” as originally stated), “may be referred to *R. ecuadorensis*”. However, given the absence of direct examination of the specimen by Mueses-Cisneros et al. (2012), its developmental stage, inconsistencies in the collection locality, and the tentative nature of this assignment, we opted to remove the species from the Brazilian species list.

•*Rhinella jimi* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Rhinella diptycha* (Pereyra et al., 2021).

•*Rhinella scitula* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Rhinella stanlaidi* (Fouquet et al., 2024b).

Centrolenidae

•*Vitreorana uranoscopa* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Vitreorana parvula* (Zucchetti & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2024).

Ceratophryidae

•*Lepidobatrachus asper* – The population from the municipality of Porto Murtinho, state of Mato Grosso, which was previously identified as *L. asper* by Sugai et al. (2013), is now reassigned to *Lepidobatrachus laevis* (see Brusquetti et al., 2018).

Craugastoridae

•*Pristimantis conspicillatus* – The species is only known with certainty from Colombia and Ecuador, with no confirmed records for Brazil (Fouquet et al., 2022b).

•*Pristimantis eurydactylus* – The species' occurrence in Brazil remains unconfirmed, as specimens previously assigned to *P. eurydactylus* show diagnostic overlap with *P. diadematus* and lack clear morphological or genetic evidence supporting their identification (Moraes et al., 2022a).

•*Pristimantis marmoratus* – As currently known, *P. marmoratus* is restricted to the western portion of Guiana Shield, in Venezuela and Guyana (Kok et al., 2018; Fouquet et al., 2022c). Populations treated as *P. marmoratus* in the states of Pará and Amapá were recently evaluated, leading to the revalidation of *Pristimantis grandoculis* and the description of *Pristimantis crepitaculus* (Fouquet et al., 2022c). However, the presence of the species in Brazil is likely, since the species occurs close to the national borders of the state of Roraima (Kok et al., 2018).

•*Pristimantis pluvian* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Pristimantis fenestratus* (Fouquet et al., 2022b).

•*Pristimantis variabilis* – Previous records of this species in Brazil were based on two sources. Firstly, Heyer (1977) reported *Pristimantis* nr. (near) *variabilis* in the state of Amazonas, specifically in the municipalities of Mucuripe and Tapauá. However, these records were not identified to the species level and lack voucher specimens. Secondly, Souza (2003), in his PhD dissertation, reported the occurrence of *P. variabilis* in the state of Acre. Nevertheless, these records were not included in a subsequent publication by the same author with the same dataset (Souza, 2009), suggesting that the earlier identification was not sustained.

•*Pristimantis academicus*, *Pristimantis altamazonicus*, *Pristimantis delius*, *Pristimantis diadematus*, *Pristimantis martiae* and *Pristimantis ventrimarmoratus* – There are no confirmed records of these species in Brazil (see Mônico et al., 2024).

Dendrobatidae

•*Ranitomeya sirensis* – Populations from the state of Acre and Amazonas previously identified as *R. sirensis* correspond to the recently described *Ranitomeya hwata* (Twomey et al., 2025).

Eleutherodactylidae

•*Adelophryne gutturosa* – Previous records of *A. gutturosa* from the state of Amapá are in fact *A. amapaensis* (see Taucce et al., 2020).

Hylidae

•*Boana alfaroi* – According to Fouquet et al. (2021a) the population previously identified as *B. alfaroi* by Carvalho et al. (2017) is *Boana steinbachi*.

•*Boana benitezi* – Populations from Vila Pacaraima, state of Roraima, previously identified as *B. benitezi* by Heyer (1994) were assigned to *Boana tepuiana* by Barrio-Amorós & Brewer-Carias (2008).

•*Boana fasciata* – Species restricted to the Andean slopes of Ecuador and Peru (Camminer & Ron, 2014; Fouquet et al., 2021a). At least part of the previous records from Acre, Amapá, Amazonas, Mato Grosso, Pará, and Rondônia correspond to one of these three species: *B. courtoisae*, *B. eucharis*, *B. steinbachi* (see Fouquet et al., 2021a).

•*Bokermannohyla napolii* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Bokermannohyla ravida* (Faivovich et al., 2025)

•*Dendropsophus bifurcus* – Duellman (1977) reported the species for the state of Acre, but Jungfer et al. (2010) stated that these records most likely refer to *D. salli*. More recently, *D. salli* was documented in the states of Acre and Rondônia, including photographic evidence (Melo-Sampaio & Souza, 2015). Based on these publications, there is no evidence that *D. bifurcus* occurs in Brazil.

•*Dendropsophus jimi* and *Dendropsophus rhea* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Dendropsophus cerradensis* (Nakamura et al., 2025).

•*Dendropsophus koechlini* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Dendropsophus pauiniensis* (Melo-Sampaio, 2023a).

•*Dryaderces pearsoni* – Brazilian populations currently assigned to this species represent an undescribed taxon (see Jungfer et al., 2013; Ortiz et al., 2020).

•*Scinax baumgardneri* – The species is known to occur in few localities in the Venezuelan Amazon (Barrio-Amorós et al., 2019) and available information suggests that *S. baumgardneri* has not been collected in the last 25 years (Araujo-Vieira et al., 2023). There is no evidence that the species occurs in Brazil, and previous Brazilian records lack voucher specimens (Crump, 1971; Azevedo-Ramos & Galatti, 2002).

Leptodactylidae

•*Leptodactylus sertanejo* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Leptodactylus jolyi* (Caramaschi et al., 2024).

•*Leptodactylus rugosus* – We are unaware of any published or voucher evidence confirming the occurrence of this species in Brazil.

Microhylidae

•*Chiasmocleis jimi* – We follow Cassundé et al. (2022) and Fouquet et al. (2022a) in maintaining the synonymy of *C. jimi* with *C. hudsoni*.

•*Chiasmocleis haddadi* – Populations from the state of Amapá, previously identified as *C. haddadi* (e.g. Peloso et al., 2014; Taucce et al., 2022), are assigned to the recently described *Chiasmocleis jacki* (Fouquet et al., 2022a).

•*Elachistocleis bumbameuboi* and *Elachistocleis carvalhoi* – Now considered junior synonyms of *Elachistocleis magna* (Novaes-e-Fagundes et al., 2023).

•*Elachistocleis matogrosso* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Elachistocleis bicolor* (Novaes-e-Fagundes et al., 2023).

•*Elachistocleis surumu* – Now considered a junior synonym of *Elachistocleis surinamensis* (Novaes-e-Fagundes et al., 2023).

•*Otophryne pyburni* – The distribution of this species was restricted to the western portion of the Guiana Shield in a recent study (Fouquet et al., 2021b), with no known records in Brazil. Therefore, records from the states of Amazonas, Pará and Amapá (e.g. Carvalho et al., 2007; Cassundé et al., 2022; Taucce et al., 2022) correspond to lineages not closely related to *O. pyburni* (Fouquet et al., 2021b).

•*Synapturanus salseri* - The species is only known with certainty from Timbó, Vaupés, Colombia, and surroundings (Fouquet et al., 2021b). At least part of the previous records in Amazonas state corresponds to the recently described *Synapturanus ajuricaba* (Fouquet et al., 2021c).

Odontophrynidae

•*Odontophrynus americanus* - The Brazilian populations previously assigned to this species belong to the recently revalidated species *Odontophrynus asper* (Rosset et al., 2022) or *O. toledo* (Moroti et al., 2022).

C) Species added to the Brazilian list after Segalla et al. (2021) through taxonomic changes or range extensions

Aromobatidae

•*Dryadobates alagoanus*, *Dryadobates capixaba*, *Dryadobates carioca* - Removed from the synonymy with *Dryadobates olfersioides* (Grant et al., 2025).

Bufonidae

•*Amazophrynella siona* - Recorded in the state of Amazonas (Moraes et al., 2022b).

•*Melanophryniscus formosus* - Populations from the coastal Atlantic Forest of Rio Grande do Sul and southern Santa Catarina previously referred to as *M. dorsalis* correspond to *M. formosus*, which has nomenclatural priority (Langone & Lavilla, 2024).

•*Rhinella martyi* (Fig. 1A) - Removed from synonymy with *R. margaritifera* (Fouquet et al., 2024b).

•*Rhinella roqueana* (Fig. 1B) - Recorded in the states of Acre, Amazonas, Mato Grosso, Pará, and Rondônia (Fouquet et al., 2024b).

•*Rhinella stanlarii* (Fig. 1C) - Revalidated as a senior synonym of *Rhinella scitula* (Fouquet et al., 2024b).

Ceratophryidae

•*Lepidobatrachus laevis* (Fig. 1D) - Population of the municipality of Porto Murtinho, state of Mato Grosso, previously identified as *L. asper* (Sugai et al., 2013) found to

be *Lepidobatrachus laevis* (Brusquetti et al., 2018).

Craugastoridae

•*Pristimantis espedeus* - Recorded in state of Amapá (Vacher et al., 2020; Taucce et al., 2022).

•*Pristimantis grandoculis* - Revalidated by Fouquet et al. (2022c).

•*Pristimantis koehleri* - Recorded in the states of Rondônia, Amazonas and Pará (Fouquet et al., 2022b).

•*Pristimantis lirellus* - *Pristimantis lirellus*, *Pristimantis okmoui* and several unidentified sequences were considered as possible synonyms and a single OTU by Mônico et al. (2024). Thus, this study reported populations treated as *P. lirellus/okmoui* for the state of Acre. We include these populations here as *P. lirellus*, since this species would be the senior synonym, in addition to the fact that the Acre populations are closer to the type locality of this species.

Dendrobatidae

•*Ranitomeya cyanovittata* - Recorded in the state of Acre (Mônico et al., 2025a).

Hylidae

•*Boana steinbachi* (Fig. 1E) - Recorded in the states of Acre, Amazonas and Pará (Fouquet et al., 2021a).

•*Bokermannohyla feioi* (Fig. 1F) - Removed from the synonymy with *Bokermannohyla nanuzae* (Brunes et al., 2023).

•*Dendropsophus arndti* (Fig. 1G) - Recorded in the state of Rondônia (Pirani et al., 2020).

•*Dendropsophus frosti* (Fig. 1H) - Recorded in the state of Amazonas (Koch et al., 2023).

•*Dendropsophus goughi* - Removed from the synonymy with *Dendropsophus microcephalus* (Orrico et al., 2025)

•*Dendropsophus reichlei* - Recorded in the state of Rondônia (Oliveira & Souza, 2021).

Figure 1. Species recorded in Brazil after the list published by Segalla et al. (2021): (a) *Rhinella marty*, (b) *Rhinella roqueana*, (c) *Rhinella stanlaidi*, (d) *Lepidobatrachus laevis*, (e) *Boana steinbachi*, (f) *Bokermannohyla feioi*, (g) *Dendropsophus arndti*, (h) *Dendropsophus frosti*, (i) *Scinax kennedyi*, (j) *Odontophrynus asper*. Photos by: AP Lima (a), DJ Santana (b, c, d, f, g, i); LO Drummond (d, j); ED Koch (h).

•*Dendropsophus shiwiarum* – Recorded in the state of Acre (Moravec et al., 2025).

•*Osteocephalus heyeri* – Recorded in the state of Amazonas (Melo-Sampaio et al., 2021).

•*Osteocephalus yasuni* – Recorded in the state of Acre (Jungfer et al., 2013).

•*Scinax chiquitanus* – Recorded in the state of Rondônia

(Ferrão et al., 2016; Araujo-Vieira et al., 2023).

•*Scinax coerulea* – Removed from the synonymy with *Scinax x-signatus* (Suárez-Mayorga, 2022).

•*Scinax jolyi* – Recorded in the states of Amapá and Amazonas (Taucce et al., 2022; Araujo-Vieira et al., 2023).

•*Scinax kennedyi* (Fig. 1I) – Recorded in the state of Roraima (Lopes & Giaretta, 2022).

Leptodactylidae

•*Leptodactylus gualambensis*– Removed from the synonymy with *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Brusquetti et al., 2025)

Odontophrynidae

•*Odontophrynus asper* (Fig. 1J) – Revalidated species by Rosset et al. (2022).

D) The updated list of amphibians of Brazil

In this section we present the final compilation of amphibian species with confirmed records in Brazil, including invasive species and those that are extinct or presumably extinct. Numbers in parentheses indicate the number of genera or species within each respective taxon. New entries relative to Segalla et al. (2021) are highlighted in red, and the corresponding bibliographic references are listed in the References section.

AMPHIBIA (125/1251)

ANURA (111/1206)

Allophrynidae (1/3)

•*Allophryne relict*a Caramaschi, Orrico, Faivovich, Dias & Solé, 2013

•*Allophryne resplendens* Castroviejo-Fisher, Pérez-Pena, Padial & Guayasamin, 2012

•*Allophryne ruthveni* Gaige, 1926

Alsodidae (1/1)

•*Limnomedusa macroglossa* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)

Aromobatidae (3/46)

Allobatinae (2/42)

•*Allobates albiventris* Souza, Ferrão, Kaefer, Cunha-

Machado, Melo-Sampaio, Hanken & Lima, 2023

- Allobates bacurau* Simões, 2016
- Allobates brunneus* (Cope, 1887)
- Allobates caeruleodactylus* (Lima & Caldwell, 2001)
- Allobates caldwella* Lima, Ferrão & Silva, 2020
- Allobates carajas* Simões, Rojas & Lima, 2019
- Allobates conspicuus* (Morales, 2002)
- Allobates crombiei* (Morales, 2002)
- Allobates femoralis* (Boulenger, 1884)
- Allobates flaviventris* Melo-Sampaio, Souza & Peloso, 2013
- Allobates fuscillus* (Morales, 2002)
- Allobates gasconi* (Morales, 2002)

- Allobates goianus* (Bokermann, 1975)
- Allobates grillicantus* Moraes & Lima, 2021
- Allobates grillisimilis* Simões, Sturaro, Peloso & Lima, 2013
- Allobates hodli* Simões, Lima & Farias, 2010
- Allobates juami* Simões, Gagliardi-Urrutia, Rojas-Runjaic & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2018
- Allobates kamilae* Ferrão, Hanken & Lima, 2022
- Allobates magnussoni* Lima, Simões & Kaefer, 2014
- Allobates marchesianus* (Melin, 1941)
- Allobates masniger* (Morales, 2002)
- Allobates myersi* (Pyburn, 1981)
- Allobates nidicola* (Caldwell & Lima, 2003)
- Allobates nunciatus* Moraes, Pavan & Lima, 2019
- Allobates pacaas* Melo-Sampaio, Prates, Peloso, Recoder, Dal Vechio, Marques-Souza & Rodrigues, 2020
- Allobates paleci* Silva, Marques, Folly & Santana, 2022 (Fig 2A)
- Allobates paleovarzensis* Lima, Caldwell, Biavati & Montanarin, 2010
- Allobates ripicolus* Fouquet, Ferrão & Jairam, 2023
- Allobates subfolionidificans* (Lima, Sanchez & Souza, 2007)
- Allobates sumtuosus* (Morales, 2002)
- Allobates tapajos* Lima, Simões & Kaefer, 2015
- Allobates tinae* Melo-Sampaio, Oliveira & Prates, 2018
- Allobates trilineatus* (Boulenger, 1884)
- Allobates vanzolinius* (Morales, 2002)
- Allobates velocicantus* Souza, Ferrão, Hanken & Lima, 2020
- Dryadobates alagoanus* (Bokermann, 1967)
- Dryadobates bokermanni* Grant, Lyra, Hofreiter, Preick, Barlow, Verdade & Rodrigues, 2025

- Dryadobates capixaba* (Bokermann, 1967)
- Dryadobates carioca* (Bokermann, 1967)
- Dryadobates erythropus* Grant & Pinheiro, 2025
- Dryadobates lutzi* Grant, Lyra, Hofreiter, Preick, Barlow, Verdade & Rodrigues, 2025
- Dryadobates olfersioides* (Lutz, 1925)

Anomaloglossinae (1/5)

- Anomaloglossus apiau* Fouquet, Souza, Nunes, Kok, Curcio, Carvalho, Grant & Rodrigues, 2015
- Anomaloglossus baobatrachus* (Boistel & de Massari, 1999)
- Anomaloglossus stepheni* (Martins, 1989)
- Anomaloglossus tamacuarensis* (Myers & Donnelly, 1997)
- Anomaloglossus tepequem* Fouquet, Souza, Nunes, Kok, Curcio, Carvalho, Grant & Rodrigues, 2015

Brachycephalidae (2/83)

- Brachycephalus actaeus* Monteiro, Condez, Garcia, Comitti, Amaral & Haddad, 2018
- Brachycephalus albolineatus* Bornschein, Ribeiro, Blackburn, Stanley & Pie, 2016
- Brachycephalus alipioi* Pombal & Gasparini, 2006
- Brachycephalus auroguttatus* Ribeiro, Firkowski, Bornschein & Pie, 2015
- Brachycephalus boticario* Pie, Bornschein, Firkowski, Belmonte-Lopes & Ribeiro 2015
- Brachycephalus brunneus* Ribeiro, Alves, Haddad & Reis, 2005
- Brachycephalus bufonoides* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920
- Brachycephalus clarissae* Folly, Vrcibradic, Siqueira, Rocha, Machado, Lopes & Pombal Jr., 2022
- Brachycephalus coloratus* Ribeiro, Blackburn, Stanley, Pie & Bornschein, 2017
- Brachycephalus crispus* Condez, Clemente-Carvalho, Haddad, & Reis 2014
- Brachycephalus curupira* Ribeiro, Blackburn, Stanley, Pie & Bornschein, 2017
- Brachycephalus dacnis* Toledo, Botelho, Carrasco-Medina, Gray, Ernetti, Gama, Lyra, Blackburn, Nunes & Muscat, 2024
- Brachycephalus darkside* Guimaraes, Luz, Rocha & Feio, 2017
- Brachycephalus didactylus* (Izecksohn, 1971)
- Brachycephalus ephippium* (Spix, 1824)
- Brachycephalus ferruginus* Alves, Ribeiro, Haddad & Reis,

- 2006
- *Brachycephalus fuscolineatus* Pie, Bornschein, Firkowski, Belmonte-Lopes & Ribeiro, 2015
 - *Brachycephalus garbeanus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920
 - *Brachycephalus guarani* Clemente-Carvalho, Giaretta, Condez, Haddad & Reis, 2012
 - *Brachycephalus herculeus* Folly, Condez, Vrcibradic, Rocha, Machado, Lopes & Pombal Jr. 2024 (Fig. 2B)
 - *Brachycephalus hermogenesi* (Giaretta & Sawaya, 1998)
 - *Brachycephalus ibitinga* Condez, Monteiro, Malagoli, Trevine, Schunck, Garcia & Haddad, 2021
 - *Brachycephalus izecksohni* Ribeiro, Alves, Haddad & Reis, 2005
 - *Brachycephalus leopardus* Ribeiro, Firkowski & Pie, 2015
 - *Brachycephalus lulai* Bornschein, Pie, Nadaline, Confetti, Blackburn, Stanley, Mari, Alves, Sandretti-Silva, Lima & Ribeiro, 2025
 - *Brachycephalus margaritatus* Pombal & Izecksohn, 2011
 - *Brachycephalus mariaeterezae* Bornschein, Morato, Firkowski, Ribeiro & Pie, 2015
 - *Brachycephalus mirissimus* Pie, Ribeiro, Confetti, Nadaline & Bornschein, 2018
 - *Brachycephalus nanicus* Nunes, Lyra, Machado, Carrasco-Medina, Andrade, Haga, Botelho, Pedrozo, Velasco, Jacinavicius, Gray, Blackburn, Kohlsdorf, Muscat & Toledo, 2025
 - *Brachycephalus nodoterga* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920
 - *Brachycephalus olivaceus* Bornschein, Morato, Firkowski, Ribeiro & Pie, 2015
 - *Brachycephalus pernix* Pombal, Wistuba & Bornschein, 1998
 - *Brachycephalus pitanga* Alves, Sawaya, Reis & Haddad, 2009
 - *Brachycephalus pombali* Alves, Ribeiro, Haddad & Reis, 2006
 - *Brachycephalus pulex* Napoli, Caramaschi, Cruz & Dias, 2011
 - *Brachycephalus puri* Almeida-Silva, Silva-Soares, Rodrigues & Verdade, 2021
 - *Brachycephalus quiririensis* Pie & Ribeiro, 2015
 - *Brachycephalus rotenbergae* Nunes, Guimarães, Moura, Pedrozo, Moroti, Castro, Stuginski & Muscat, 2021
 - *Brachycephalus sulfuratus* Condez, Monteiro, Comitti, Garcia, Amaral & Haddad, 2016
 - *Brachycephalus tabuleiro* Mângia, Santana, Drummond, Sabagh, Ugioni, Costa & Wachlevski, 2023 (Fig. 2C)
 - *Brachycephalus toby* Haddad, Alves, Clemente-Carvalho & Reis, 2010
 - *Brachycephalus tridactylus* Garey, Lima, Hartmann & Haddad, 2012
 - *Brachycephalus verrucosus* Ribeiro, Firkowski, Bornschein & Pie, 2015
 - *Brachycephalus vertebralis* Pombal, 2001
 - *Ischnocnema abdita* Canedo & Pimenta, 2010
 - *Ischnocnema bocaina* Taucce, Zaidan, Zaher & Garcia, 2019
 - *Ischnocnema bolbodactyla* (Lutz, 1925)
 - *Ischnocnema colibri* Taucce, Canedo, Parreiras, Drummond, Nogueira-Costa & Haddad, 2018
 - *Ischnocnema concolor* Targino, Costa & Carvalho-e-Silva, 2009
 - *Ischnocnema crassa* Silva-Soares, Ferreira, Ornellas, Zocca, Caramaschi & Cruz, 2021
 - *Ischnocnema epipeda* (Heyer, 1984)
 - *Ischnocnema erythromera* (Heyer, 1984)
 - *Ischnocnema feioi* Taucce, Canedo & Haddad, 2018
 - *Ischnocnema garciai* Taucce, Canedo & Haddad, 2018
 - *Ischnocnema gehrti* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
 - *Ischnocnema gualteri* (Lutz, 1974)
 - *Ischnocnema guentheri* (Steindachner, 1864)
 - *Ischnocnema henselii* (Peters, 1870)
 - *Ischnocnema hoehnei* (Lutz, 1958)
 - *Ischnocnema holti* (Cochran, 1948)
 - *Ischnocnema izecksohni* (Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989)
 - *Ischnocnema juipoca* (Sazima & Cardoso, 1978)
 - *Ischnocnema karst* Canedo, Targino, Leite & Haddad, 2012
 - *Ischnocnema lactea* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923)
 - *Ischnocnema manezinho* (Garcia, 1996)
 - *Ischnocnema melanopygia* Targino, Costa & Carvalho-e-Silva, 2009
 - *Ischnocnema nanahallux* Brusquetti, Thomé, Canedo, Condez & Haddad, 2013
 - *Ischnocnema nasuta* (Lutz, 1925)
 - *Ischnocnema nigriventris* (Lutz, 1925)
 - *Ischnocnema octavioi* (Bokermann, 1965)
 - *Ischnocnema oea* (Heyer, 1984)
 - *Ischnocnema paranaensis* (Langone & Segalla, 1996)
 - *Ischnocnema parnaso* Taucce, Canedo, Parreiras, Drummond, Nogueira-Costa & Haddad, 2018

- Ischnocnema parva* (Girard, 1853)
 - Ischnocnema penaxavantinho* Giaretta, Toffoli & Oliveira, 2007
 - Ischnocnema pusilla* (Bokermann, 1967)
 - Ischnocnema randorum* (Heyer, 1985)
 - Ischnocnema rubridactyla* Silva-Soares, Campos, Pirovani-Silva, Costa & Monjardim 2026
 - Ischnocnema sambaqui* (Castanho & Haddad, 2000)
 - Ischnocnema spanios* (Heyer, 1985)
 - Ischnocnema surda* Canedo, Pimenta, Leite & Caramaschi, 2010
 - Ischnocnema venancioi* (Lutz, 1958)
 - Ischnocnema verrucosa* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)
 - Ischnocnema vizottoi* Martins & Haddad, 2010
- Bufonidae (9/98)**
- Adhaerobufo ceratophrys* (Boulenger, 1882)
 - Amazophrynella bilinguis* Kaefer, Rojas-Zamora, Ferrão, Farias & Lima, 2019
 - Amazophrynella bokermanni* (Izecksohn, 1994)
 - Amazophrynella gardai* Mângia, Koroiva & Santana, 2020
 - Amazophrynella manaos* Rojas, Carvalho, Gordo, Ávila, Farias & Hrbek, 2014
 - Amazophrynella minuta* (Melin, 1941)
 - Amazophrynella moisesii* Rojas-Zamora, Fouquet, Ron, Hernández-Ruz, Melo-Sampaio, Chaparro, Vogt, Carvalho, Pinheiro, Ávila, Farias, Gordo & Hrbek, 2018
 - Amazophrynella siona* Rojas-Zamora, Fouquet, Ron, Hernández-Ruz, Melo-Sampaio, Chaparro, Vogt, Carvalho, Pinheiro, Ávila, Farias, Gordo & Hrbek, 2017
 - Amazophrynella teko* Rojas-Zamora, Fouquet, Ron, Hernández-Ruz, Melo-Sampaio, Chaparro, Vogt, Carvalho, Pinheiro, Ávila, Farias, Gordo & Hrbek, 2018
 - Amazophrynella vote* Ávila, Carvalho, Gordo, Kawashita-Ribeiro & Morais, 2012
 - Amazophrynella xinguensis* Rojas-Zamora, Fouquet, Ron, Hernández-Ruz, Melo-Sampaio, Chaparro, Vogt, Carvalho, Pinheiro, Ávila, Farias, Gordo & Hrbek, 2018
 - Atelopus flavescens* Duméril & Bibron, 1841
 - Atelopus franciscus* Lescure, 1974
 - Atelopus hoogmoedi* Lescure, 1974
 - Atelopus manauensis* Jorge, Ferrão & Lima, 2020
 - Dendrophryniscus berthallutzae* Izecksohn, 1994
 - Dendrophryniscus brevipollicatus* Jiménez de la Espada, 187
 - Dendrophryniscus carvalhoi* Izecksohn, 1994
 - Dendrophryniscus cuca* Neves, Lima, Koroiva, Nali & Santana, 2023 (Fig. 2D)
 - Dendrophryniscus davori* Cruz, Caramaschi, Fusinato, & Brasileiro, 2019
 - Dendrophryniscus haddadi* Cruz, Caramaschi, Fusinato, & Brasileiro, 2019
 - Dendrophryniscus imitator* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)
 - Dendrophryniscus izecksohni* Cruz, Caramaschi, Fusinato, & Brasileiro, 2019
 - Dendrophryniscus jureia* Cruz, Caramaschi, Fusinato, & Brasileiro, 2019
 - Dendrophryniscus krausae* Cruz & Fusinato, 2008
 - Dendrophryniscus lauroi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
 - Dendrophryniscus leucomystax* Izecksohn, 1968
 - Dendrophryniscus oreites* Recoder, Teixeira, Cassimiro, Camacho & Rodrigues, 2010
 - Dendrophryniscus organensis* Carvalho-e-Silva, Mongin, Izecksohn & Carvalho-e-Silva, 2010
 - Dendrophryniscus proboscideus* (Boulenger, 1882)
 - Dendrophryniscus skuki* (Caramaschi, 2012)
 - Dendrophryniscus stawiarskyi* Izecksohn, 1994
 - Frostius erythrophthalmus* Pimenta & Caramaschi, 2007
 - Frostius pernambucensis* (Bokermann, 1962)
 - Melanophryniscus admirabilis* Di Bernardo, Maneyro & Grillo, 2006
 - Melanophryniscus alipioi* Langone, Segalla, Bornschein & de Sá, 2008
 - Melanophryniscus atroluteus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)
 - Melanophryniscus biancae* Bornschein, Baldo, Pie, Firkowski, Ribeiro & Corrêa, 2015
 - Melanophryniscus cambaraensis* Braun & Braun, 1979
 - Melanophryniscus devincenzii* Klappenbach, 1968
 - Melanophryniscus formosus* (Gliesch, 1925)
 - Melanophryniscus fulvoguttatus* (Mertens, 1937)
 - Melanophryniscus klappenbachi* (Mertens, 1937)
 - Melanophryniscus macrogranulosus* Braun, 1973
 - Melanophryniscus milanoi* Baldo, Bornschein, Pie, Firkowski, Ribeiro, Belmonte-Lopes, 2015
 - Melanophryniscus montevidensis* (Philippi, 1902)
 - Melanophryniscus moreirae* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)
 - Melanophryniscus pachyrhynchus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)
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- Melanophryniscus peritus* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2011
 - Melanophryniscus sanmartini* Klappenbach, 1968
 - Melanophryniscus setiba* Peloso, Faivovich, Grant, Gasparini & Haddad, 2012
 - Melanophryniscus simplex* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2002
 - Melanophryniscus spectabilis* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2002
 - Melanophryniscus tumifrons* (Boulenger, 1905)
 - Melanophryniscus vilavelhensis* Steinback-Padilha, 2009
 - Melanophryniscus xanthostomus* Baldo, Bornschein, Pie, Ribeiro, Firkowski, & Morato, 2015
 - Oreophrynella quelchii* Boulenger, 1895
 - Oreophrynella weiassipuensis* Senaris, Do Nascimento & Villarreal, 2005
 - Rhaebo guttatus* (Schneider, 1799)
 - Rhinella achavali* (Maneyro, Arrieta & de Sá, 2004)
 - Rhinella acutirostris* (Spix, 1824)
 - Rhinella arenarum* (Hensel, 1867)
 - Rhinella azarai* (Gallardo, 1965)
 - Rhinella bergi* (Céspedes, 2000)
 - Rhinella casconi* Roberto, Brito & Thomé, 2014
 - Rhinella castaneotica* (Caldwell, 1991)
 - Rhinella cerradensis* Maciel, Brandão, Campos & Sebben, 2007
 - Rhinella crucifer* (Wied, 1821)
 - Rhinella dapsilis* (Myers & Carvalho, 1945)
 - Rhinella diptycha* (Cope, 1862)
 - Rhinella dorbignyi* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)
 - Rhinella exostolica* Ferrão, Lima, Ron, Santos & Hanken, 2020
 - Rhinella granulosa* (Spix, 1824)
 - Rhinella henseli* (Lutz, 1934)
 - Rhinella hoogmoedi* Caramaschi & Pombal, 2006
 - Rhinella icterica* (Spix, 1824)
 - Rhinella inopina* Vaz-Silva, Valdujo & Pombal, 2012
 - Rhinella lescurei* Fouquet, Gaucher, Blanc & Vélez-Rodriguez, 2007
 - Rhinella magnussoni* Lima, Menin & Araújo, 2007
 - Rhinella major* (Muller & Helmich, 1936)
 - Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768)
 - Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758)
 - Rhinella martyi* Fouquet, Gaucher, Blanc & Vélez-Rodriguez, 2007
 - Rhinella merianae* (Gallardo, 1965)
 - Rhinella mirandaribeiroi* (Gallardo, 1965)
 - Rhinella nattereri* (Bokermann, 1967)
 - Rhinella ocellata* (Günther, 1858)
 - Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824)
 - Rhinella parecis* Ávila, Morais, Perez, Pansonato, Carvalho, Rojas-Zamora, Gordo & Farias, 2020
 - Rhinella poeppigii* (Tschudi, 1845)
 - Rhinella proboscidea* (Spix, 1824)
 - Rhinella pygmaea* (Myers & Carvalho, 1952)
 - Rhinella roqueana* (Melin, 1941)
 - Rhinella rubescens* (Lutz, 1925)
 - Rhinella sebbeni* Vaz-Silva, Maciel, Bastos & Pombal, 2015
 - Rhinella stanlaidi* (Lötters and Köhler, 2000)
 - Rhinella teotoniensis* Ferrão, Souza, Hanken & Lima, 2022
 - Rhinella veredas* (Brandão, Maciel & Sebben, 2007)
- Caligophrynidae (1/1)**
- Caligophryne doylei* Fouquet, Kok, Recoder, Prates, Camacho, Marques-Souza, Ghellere, McDiarmid & Rodrigues 2024
- Centrolenidae (4/17)**
- Centroleninae (3/9)**
- Cochranella resplendens* (Lynch & Duellman, 1973)
 - Teratohyla adenocheira* (Harvey & Noonan, 2005)
 - Teratohyla midas* (Lynch & Duellman, 1973)
 - Vitreorana assuh* Zucchetti, Rojas-Padilla, Dias, Solé, Orrico & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2023
 - Vitreorana baliomma* Pontes, Caramaschi & Pombal, 2014
 - Vitreorana eurygnatha* (Lutz, 1925)
 - Vitreorana franciscana* Santana, Barros, Pontes & Feio, 2015
 - Vitreorana parvula* (Boulenger, 1895)
 - Vitreorana ritae* (Lutz, 1952)
- Hyalinobatrachinae (1/8)**
- Hyalinobatrachium cappellei* (van Lidth de Jeude, 1904)
 - Hyalinobatrachium carlesvilai* Castroviejo-Fisher, Padiál, Chaparro, Aguayo & De la Riva, 2009
 - Hyalinobatrachium iaspidiense* (Ayarzaguena, 1992)
 - Hyalinobatrachium mondolfii* Senaris & Ayarzaguena, 2001
 - Hyalinobatrachium muiraquitán* Oliveira & Hernández-Ruz, 2017
 - Hyalinobatrachium munozorum* (Lynch & Duellman, 1973)
 - Hyalinobatrachium taylori* (Goin, 1968)
 - Hyalinobatrachium tricolor* Castroviejo-Fisher, Vilà,

Ayarzagüena, Blanc & Ernst, 2011

Ceratophryidae (2/6)

- *Ceratophrys aurita* (Raddi, 1823)
- *Ceratophrys cornuta* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- *Ceratophrys cranwelli* Barrio, 1980
- *Ceratophrys joazeirensis* Mercadal de Barrio, 1986
- *Ceratophrys ornata* (Bell, 1843)
- *Lepidobatrachus laevis* Budgett, 1899

Ceuthomantidae (1/1)

- *Ceuthomantis cavernibardus* (Myers & Donnelly, 1997)

Craugastoridae (9/62)

Craugastorinae (1/3)

- *Haddadus aramunha* (Cassimiro, Verdade & Rodrigues, 2008)
- *Haddadus binotatus* (Spix, 1824)
- *Haddadus plicifer* (Boulenger, 1888)

Holoadeninae (5/12)

- *Bahius bilineatus* (Bokermann, 1975)
- *Barycholos ternetzi* (Miranda Ribeiro, 1937)
- *Euparkerella brasiliensis* (Parker, 1926)
- *Euparkerella cochranae* Izecksohn, 1988
- *Euparkerella cryptica* Hepp, Carvalho-e-Silva, Carvalho-e-Silva & Folly, 2015
- *Euparkerella robusta* Izecksohn, 1988
- *Euparkerella tridactyla* Izecksohn, 1988
- *Holoaden bradei* Lutz, 1958
- *Holoaden luederwaldti* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920
- *Holoaden pholeter* Pombal, Siqueira, Dorigo, Vrcibradic & Rocha, 2008
- *Holoaden suarezi* Martins & Zaher, 2013
- *Phyllonastes myrmecoides* (Lynch, 1976)

Pristimantinae (2/45)

- *Oreobates antrum* Vaz-Silva, Maciel, Andrade & Amaro, 2018
- *Oreobates heterodactylus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)
- *Oreobates quixensis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872
- *Oreobates remotus* Teixeira, Amaro, Recoder, Sena & Rodrigues, 2012
- *Pristimantis acuminatus* (Shreve, 1935)

- *Pristimantis aureolineatus* (Guayasamin, Ron, Cisneros-Heredia, Lamar & McCracken, 2006)
- *Pristimantis buccinator* (Rodríguez, 1994)
- *Pristimantis campinarana* Mônico, Ferrão, Moravec, Fouquet & Lima, 2023 (Fig. 2E)
- *Pristimantis carvalhoi* (Lutz, 1952)
- *Pristimantis chiastonotus* (Lynch & Hoogmoed, 1977)
- *Pristimantis crepitaculus* Fouquet, Peloso, Jairam, Lima, Mônico, Ernst & Kok, 2022
- *Pristimantis dundeei* (Heyer & Munoz, 1999)
- *Pristimantis espedeus* Fouquet, Martínez, Courtois, Dewynter, Pineau, Gaucher, Blanc, Marty & Kok, 2013
- *Pristimantis fenestratus* (Steindachner, 1864)
- *Pristimantis fouqueti* Mônico, Courtois, Koch, Blanc, Dewynter & Kok, 2025
- *Pristimantis giorgii* Oliveira, Silva, Guimarães, Penhacek, Martínez, Rodrigues, Santana & Hernández-Ruíz, 2020
- *Pristimantis grandoculis* (Van Lidth de Jeude, 1904)
- *Pristimantis guianensis* Mônico, Ferrão, Chaparro, Fouquet & Lima, 2022 (Fig. 2F)
- *Pristimantis gutturalis* (Hoogmoed, Lynch & Lescure, 1977)
- *Pristimantis inguinalis* (Parker, 1940)
- *Pristimantis koehleri* Padial & De la Riva, 2009
- *Pristimantis lacrimosus* (Jiménez de la Espada, 1875)
- *Pristimantis lanthanites* (Lynch, 1975)
- *Pristimantis latro* Oliveira, Rodrigues, Kaefer, Pinto & Hernández-Ruz, 2017
- *Pristimantis lirellus* (Dwyer, 1995)
- *Pristimantis luscombei* (Duellman & Mendelson, 1995)
- *Pristimantis malkini* (Lynch, 1980)
- *Pristimantis memorans* (Myers & Donnelly, 1997)
- *Pristimantis moa* Oliveira, Silva, Guimarães, Penhacek, Martínez, Rodrigues, Santana & Hernández-Ruíz, 2020
- *Pristimantis ockendeni* (Boulenger, 1912)
- *Pristimantis orcus* Lehr, Catenazzi & Rodriguez, 2009
- *Pristimantis paulodutra* (Bokermann, 1975)
- *Pristimantis paulogabrieli* Melo-Sampaio 2023
- *Pristimantis peruvianus* (Melin, 1941)
- *Pristimantis pictus* Oliveira, Silva, Guimarães, Penhacek, Martínez, Rodrigues, Santana & Hernández-Ruíz, 2020
- *Pristimantis ramagii* (Boulenger, 1888)
- *Pristimantis reichlei* Padial & De La Riva, 2009
- *Pristimantis relictus* Roberto, Loebmann, Lyra, Haddad &

Ávila, 2022

- *Pristimantis rupicola* Taucce, Nascimento, Trevisan, Leite, Santana, Haddad & Napoli, 2020
- *Pristimantis skydmainos* (Flores & Rodriguez, 1997)
- *Pristimantis toftae* (Duellman, 1978)
- *Pristimantis ventrigranulosus* Maciel, Vaz-Silva, Oliveira & Padial, 2012
- *Pristimantis vilarsi* (Melin, 1941)
- *Pristimantis vinhai* (Bokermann, 1975)
- *Pristimantis zeuctotylus* (Lynch & Hoogmoed, 1977)
- *Pristimantis zimmermanae* (Heyer & Hardy, 1991)

Strabomantinae (1/1)

- *Strabomantis sulcatus* (Cope, 1874)

Cycloramphidae (2/37)

- *Cycloramphus acangan* Verdade & Rodrigues, 2003
- *Cycloramphus asper* Werner, 1899
- *Cycloramphus bandeirensis* Heyer, 1983
- *Cycloramphus bolitoglossus* (Werner, 1897)
- *Cycloramphus boraceiensis* Heyer, 1983
- *Cycloramphus brasiliensis* (Steindachner, 1864)
- *Cycloramphus carvalhoi* (Izecksohn, 1983)
- *Cycloramphus catarinensis* Heyer, 1983
- *Cycloramphus cedrensis* Heyer, 1983
- *Cycloramphus diringshofeni* Bokermann, 1957
- *Cycloramphus dubius* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)
- *Cycloramphus duseni* (Andersson, 1914)
- *Cycloramphus eleutherodactylus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)
- *Cycloramphus faustoi* Brasileiro, Haddad, Sawaya & Sazima, 2007
- *Cycloramphus fuliginosus* Tschudi, 1838
- *Cycloramphus granulatus* Lutz, 1929
- *Cycloramphus heyeri* Segalla, Berneck, Canedo, Caramaschi, Cruz, Garcia, Grant, Haddad, Lourenço, Mângia, Mott, Nascimento, Toledo, Werneck & Langone, 2021
- *Cycloramphus izecksohni* Heyer, 1983
- *Cycloramphus juimirim* Haddad & Sazima, 1989
- *Cycloramphus lithomimeticus* Silva & Ouverney 2012
- *Cycloramphus lutzorum* Heyer, 1983
- *Cycloramphus migueli* Heyer, 1988
- *Cycloramphus mirandaribeiroi* Heyer, 1983
- *Cycloramphus ohausi* Wandolleck, 1907
- *Cycloramphus organensis* Weber, Verdade, Salles, Fouquet &

Carvalho-e-Silva, 2011

- *Cycloramphus parvulus* (Girard, 1853)
- *Cycloramphus rhyakonastes* Heyer, 1983
- *Cycloramphus semipalmatus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)
- *Cycloramphus stejnegeri* (Noble, 1924)
- *Cycloramphus valae* Heyer, 1983
- *Thoropa bryomantis* Assis, Lacerda, Guimarães, Peixoto, Luna, & Feio, 2021
- *Thoropa lutzi* Cochran, 1938
- *Thoropa megatympanum* Caramaschi & Sazima, 1984
- *Thoropa miliaris* (Spix, 1824)
- *Thoropa petropolitana* (Wandolleck, 1907)
- *Thoropa saxatilis* Cocroft & Heyer, 1988
- *Thoropa taophora* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923)

Dendrobatidae (5/26)**Colostethinae (1/10)**

- *Ameerega berohoka* Vaz-Silva & Maciel, 2011
- *Ameerega braccata* (Steindachner, 1864)
- *Ameerega flavopicta* (Lutz, 1925)
- *Ameerega hahneli* (Boulenger, 1884)
- *Ameerega macero* (Rodriguez & Myers, 1993)
- *Ameerega munduruku* Neves, Silva, Akieda, Cabrera, Koroiva & Santana, 2017
- *Ameerega petersi* (Silverstone, 1976)
- *Ameerega picta* (Bibron in Tschudi, 1838)
- *Ameerega pulchripecta* (Silverstone, 1976)
- *Ameerega trivittata* (Spix, 1824)

Dendrobatinae (3/15)

- *Adelphobates castaneoticus* (Caldwell & Myers, 1990)
- *Adelphobates galactonotus* (Steindachner, 1864)
- *Adelphobates quinquevittatus* (Steindachner, 1864)
- *Dendrobates leucomelas* Steindachner, 1864
- *Dendrobates tinctorius* (Cuvier, 1797)
- *Ranitomeya aetherea* Koch, Mônico, Dayrell, Ferreira, Dantas, Moravec & Lima, 2025
- *Ranitomeya amazonica* (Schulte, 1999)
- *Ranitomeya aquamarina* Mônico, Koch, Dayrell, Moravec & Lima, 2025
- *Ranitomeya cyanovittata* Pérez-Peña, Chávez, Twomey & Brown, 2010
- *Ranitomeya defleri* Twomey & Brown, 2009
- *Ranitomeya hwata* Twomey, Melo-Sampaio, Brown,

Castroviejo-Fisher, Gagliardi-Urrutia, Padial, Gutiérrez & Chaparro, 2025

- Ranitomeya toraro* Brown, Caldwell, Twomey, Melo-Sampaio & Souza, 2011
- Ranitomeya uakarii* Brown, Schulte & Summers, 2006
- Ranitomeya vanzolinii* (Myers, 1982)
- Ranitomeya variabilis* (Zimmermann & Zimmermann, 1988)

Hyloxalinae (1/1)

- Hyloxalus chlorocraspedus* (Caldwell, 2005)

Eleutherodactylidae (3/13)**Eleutherodactylinae (1/1)**

- Eleutherodactylus johnstonei* Barbour, 1914

Phyzelaphryninae (2/12)

- Adelophryne adiastrata* Hoogmoed & Lescure, 1984
- Adelophryne amapaensis* Taucce, Costa-Campos, Haddad & Carvalho, 2020
- Adelophryne baturitensis* Hoogmoed, Borges & Cascon, 1994
- Adelophryne glandulata* Lourenco-de-Moraes, Ferreira, Fouquet & Bastos, 2014
- Adelophryne maranguapensis* Hoogmoed, Borges & Cascon, 1994
- Adelophryne meridionalis* Santana, Fonseca, Neves & Carvalho 2012
- Adelophryne michelin* Lourenco-de-Moraes, Dias, Mira-Mendes, Oliveira, Barth, Ruas, Vences, Solé & Bastos, 2018
- Adelophryne mucronata* Lourenco-de-Moraes, Solé & Toledo, 2012
- Adelophryne nordestina* Lourenço-de-Moraes, Lisboa, Drummond, Moura, Moura, Lyra, Guarnieri, Mott, Hoogmoed, & Santana, 2021(Fig. 2G)
- Adelophryne pachydactyla* Hoogmoed, Borges & Cascon, 1994
- Phyzelaphryne miriamae* Heyer, 1977
- Phyzelaphryne nimio* Simões, Costa, Rojas-Runjaic, Gagliardi-Urrutia, Sturaro, Peloso & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2018

Hemiphractidae (5/21)

- Alainia albolineata* (Lutz & Lutz, 1939)
- Alainia ernestoi* (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920)

- Alainia fulvorufa* (Andersson, 1911)
- Alainia microdiscus* (Andersson, 1910)
- Eothecca fissipes* (Boulenger, 1888)
- Eothecca flamma* (Juncá & Nunes, 2008)
- Eothecca megacephala* (Izecksohn, Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 2009)
- Eothecca prasina* (Teixeira, Dal Vechio, Recoder, Carnaval, Strangas, Damasceno, Sena & Rodrigues, 2012)
- Eothecca pulchra* (Caramaschi & Rodrigues, 2007)
- Eothecca recava* (Teixeira, Dal Vechio, Recoder, Carnaval, Strangas, Damasceno, Sena & Rodrigues, 2012)
- Fritziana fissilis* (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920)
- Fritziana goeldii* (Boulenger, 1895)
- Fritziana izecksohni* Folly, Hepp & Carvalho-e-Silva, 2018
- Fritziana mitus* Walker, Wachlevski, Nogueira-Costa, Garcia & Haddad, 2018
- Fritziana ohausi* (Wandolleck, 1907)
- Fritziana tonimi* Walker, Gasparini & Haddad, 2016
- Fritziana ulei* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
- Hemiphractus helioi* Sheil & Mendelson, 2001
- Hemiphractus scutatus* (Spix, 1824)
- Stefania neblinae* Carvalho, MacCulloch, Bonora & Vogt, 2010
- Stefania tamacuarina* Myers & Donnelly, 1997

Hylidae (21/392)**Hylinae (21/392)****incertae sedis (1/1)**

- “*Hyla*” *imitator* (Barbour & Dunn, 1921)

Cophomantini (3/115)

- Aplastodiscus albofrenatus* (Lutz, 1924)
- Aplastodiscus albosignatus* (Lutz & Lutz, 1938)
- Aplastodiscus arildae* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1987)
- Aplastodiscus aulophonus* Marinho, Santos, Faivovich, Lyra, Giaretta, Haddad & Carvalho, 2024
- Aplastodiscus cavicola* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1985)
- Aplastodiscus cochraniae* (Mertens, 1952)
- Aplastodiscus ehrhardti* (Müller, 1924)
- Aplastodiscus eugenioi* (Carvalho-e-Silva & Carvalho-e-Silva, 2005)
- Aplastodiscus flumineus* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1985)

Figure 2. Species described since the list published by Segalla et al. (2021): (a) *Allobates paleci*, (b) *Brachycephalus herculeus*, (c) *Brachycephalus tabuleiro*, (d) *Dendrophryniscus cuca*, (e) *Pristimantis campinarana*, (f) *Pristimantis guianensis*, (g) *Adelophryne nordestina*, (h) *Boana guarinimirim*, (i) *Ololygon pixinguinha*, (j) *Phantasmarana curucutuensis*. Photos by: LA Silva (a); DJ Santana (b, c, d, h); AT Mônico (e, f); LO Drummond (g); JVA Lacerda (i); L Malagoli (j).

- *Aplastodiscus heterophonius* Pinheiro, Pezzuti, Berneck, Lyra, Lima & Leite, 2021
- *Aplastodiscus ibirapitanga* (Cruz, Pimenta & Silvano, 2003)
- *Aplastodiscus leucopygius* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1985)
- *Aplastodiscus lutzorum* Berneck, Giaretta, Brandão, Cruz & Haddad, 2017
- *Aplastodiscus musicus* (Lutz, 1949)

- *Aplastodiscus perviridis* Lutz, 1950
- *Aplastodiscus sibilatus* (Cruz, Pimenta & Silvano, 2003)
- *Aplastodiscus weygoldti* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1987)
- *Boana albomarginata* (Spix, 1824)
- *Boana albopunctata* (Spix, 1824)
- *Boana appendiculata* (Boulenger, 1882)
- *Boana atlantica* (Caramaschi & Velosa, 1996)
- *Boana bischoffi* (Boulenger, 1887)
- *Boana boans* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- *Boana botumirim* (Caramaschi, Cruz & Nascimento, 2009)
- *Boana buriti* (Caramaschi & Cruz, 1999)
- *Boana caiapo* Pinheiro, Cintra, Valdujo, Silva, Martins, Silva & Garcia, 2018
- *Boana caingua* (Carrizo, 1991)
- *Boana caipora* (Antunes, Faivovich & Haddad, 2008)
- *Boana calcarata* (Troschel in Schomburgk, 1848)
- *Boana cambui* (Pinheiro, Pezzuti, Leite, Garcia, Haddad & Faivovich, 2016)
- *Boana cinerascens* (Spix, 1824)
- *Boana cipoensis* (Lutz, 1968)
- *Boana claresignata* (Lutz & Lutz, 1939)
- *Boana clepsydra* (Lutz, 1925)
- *Boana courtoisae* Fouquet, Marinho, Réjaud, Carvalho, Caminer, Jansen, Rainha, Rodrigues, Werneck, Lima, Hrbek, Giaretta, Venegas, Chávez & Ron, 2021
- *Boana crepitans* (Wied, 1824)
- *Boana curupi* (Garcia, Faivovich & Haddad, 2007)
- *Boana cymbalum* (Bokermann, 1963)
- *Boana dentei* (Bokermann, 1967)
- *Boana diabolica* (Fouquet, Martinez, Zeidler, Courtois, Gaucher, Blanc, Lima, Souza, Rodrigues & Kok, 2016)
- *Boana ericae* (Caramaschi & Cruz, 2000)
- *Boana eucharis* Fouquet, Marinho, Réjaud, Carvalho, Caminer, Jansen, Rainha, Rodrigues, Werneck, Lima, Hrbek, Giaretta, Venegas, Chávez & Ron, 2021
- *Boana exastis* (Caramaschi & Rodriguez, 2003)
- *Boana faber* (Wied, 1821)
- *Boana freicanecae* (Carnaval & Peixoto, 2004)
- *Boana geographica* (Spix, 1824)
- *Boana goiana* (Lutz, 1968)

- Boana gracilis* (Melin, 1941)
 - Boana guarinimirim* Marinho, Bang, Vidigal & Giaretta, 2022 (Fig. 2H)
 - Boana guentheri* (Boulenger, 1886)
 - Boana hobbsi* (Cochran & Goin, 1970)
 - Boana icamiaba* Peloso, Oliveira, Sturaro, Rodrigues, Lima, Bitar, Wheeler & Aleixo, 2018
 - Boana itajahy* Pinheiro, Dallacorte, Thompson, Comitti, Nakamura & Garcia, 2024
 - Boana jaguariaivensis* (Caramaschi, Cruz & Segalla, 2010)
 - Boana joaquinii* (Lutz, 1968)
 - Boana lanciformis* (Cope, 1871)
 - Boana leptolineata* (P. Braun & C. Braun, 1977)
 - Boana leucocheila* (Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2003)
 - Boana lundii* (Burmeister, 1856)
 - Boana maculateralis* (Caminer & Ron, 2014)
 - Boana marginata* (Boulenger, 1887)
 - Boana microderma* (Pyburn, 1977)
 - Boana multifasciata* (Günther, 1859)
 - Boana nympha* (Faivovich, Moravec, Cisneros-Heredia & Kohler, 2006)
 - Boana ornatissima* (Noble, 1923)
 - Boana paranaiba* (Carvalho, Giaretta & Facure, 2010)
 - Boana pardalis* (Spix, 1824)
 - Boana poaju* (Garcia, Peixoto & Haddad, 2008)
 - Boana polytaenia* (Cope, 1870)
 - Boana pombali* (Caramaschi, Pimenta & Feio, 2004)
 - Boana prasina* (Burmeister, 1856)
 - Boana pulchella* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)
 - Boana punctata* (Schneider, 1799)
 - Boana quiriri* Pinheiro, Dallacorte, Thompson, Comitti, Nakamura & Garcia, 2024
 - Boana raniceps* (Cope, 1862)
 - Boana secedens* (Lutz, 1963)
 - Boana semiguttata* (Lutz, 1925)
 - Boana semilineata* (Spix, 1824)
 - Boana steinbachi* Boulenger, 1905
 - Boana stellae* (Kwet, 2008)
 - Boana stenocephala* (Caramaschi & Cruz, 1999)
 - Boana tepuiana* (Barrio-Amorós & Brewer-Carias, 2008)
 - Boana ventrimaculata* Caminer & Ron, 2020
 - Boana wavrini* (Parker, 1936)
 - Boana xerophylla* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)
 - Bokermannohyla ahenea* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 2004)
 - Bokermannohyla alvarengai* (Bokermann, 1956)
 - Bokermannohyla astartea* (Bokermann, 1967)
 - Bokermannohyla capra* Napoli & Pimenta, 2009
 - Bokermannohyla caramaschii* (Napoli, 2005)
 - Bokermannohyla carvalhoi* (Peixoto, 1981)
 - Bokermannohyla circumdata* (Cope, 1871)
 - Bokermannohyla diamantina* Napoli & Juncá, 2006
 - Bokermannohyla feioi* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 2004)
 - Bokermannohyla flavopicta* Leite, Pezzuti & Garcia, 2012
 - Bokermannohyla gouveai* (Peixoto & Cruz, 1992)
 - Bokermannohyla hylax* (Heyer, 1985)
 - Bokermannohyla ibitiguara* (Cardoso, 1983)
 - Bokermannohyla ibitipoca* (Caramaschi & Feio, 1990)
 - Bokermannohyla itapoty* Lugli & Haddad, 2006
 - Bokermannohyla izecksohni* (Jim & Caramaschi, 1979)
 - Bokermannohyla juiju* Faivovich, Lugli, Lourenco & Haddad, 2009
 - Bokermannohyla langei* (Bokermann, 1965)
 - Bokermannohyla lucianae* (Napoli & Pimenta, 2003)
 - Bokermannohyla luctuosa* (Pombal & Haddad, 1993)
 - Bokermannohyla martinsi* (Bokermann, 1964)
 - Bokermannohyla nanuzae* (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973)
 - Bokermannohyla oxente* Lugli & Haddad, 2006
 - Bokermannohyla pseudopseudis* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)
 - Bokermannohyla ravidia* (Caramaschi, Napoli & Bernardes, 2001)
 - Bokermannohyla sagarana* Leite, Pezzuti & Drummond, 2011
 - Bokermannohyla sapiranga* Brandão, Magalhães, Garda, Campos, Sebben & Maciel, 2012
 - Bokermannohyla saxicola* (Bokermann, 1964)
 - Bokermannohyla sazimai* (Cardoso & Andrade, 1982)
 - Bokermannohyla vulcaniae* (Vasconcelos & Giaretta, 2005)
- ### Dendropsophini (2/75)
- Dendropsophus acreanus* (Bokermann, 1964)
 - Dendropsophus anataliasiasi* (Bokermann, 1972)
 - Dendropsophus anceps* (Lutz, 1929)

- *Dendropsophus araguaya* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1998)
- *Dendropsophus arndti* Caminer, Milá, Jansen, Fouquet, Venegas, Chávez, Lougheed & Ron, 2017
- *Dendropsophus berthalutzae* (Bokermann, 1962)
- *Dendropsophus bilobatus* Ferrão, Moravec, Hanken & Lima, 2020
- *Dendropsophus bipunctatus* (Spix, 1824)
- *Dendropsophus bokermanni* (Goin, 1960)
- *Dendropsophus branneri* (Cochran, 1948)
- *Dendropsophus brevifrons* (Duellman & Crump, 1974)
- *Dendropsophus bromeliaceus* Ferreira, Faivovich, Beard & Pombal, 2015
- *Dendropsophus cachimbo* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999)
- *Dendropsophus cerradensis* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1998)
- *Dendropsophus counani* Fouquet, Orrico, Ernest, Blanc, Martinez, Vacher, Rodrigues, Ouboter, Jairam & Ron, 2015
- *Dendropsophus cruzi* (Pombal & Bastos, 1998)
- *Dendropsophus decipiens* (Lutz, 1925)
- *Dendropsophus dutrai* (Gomes & Peixoto, 1996)
- *Dendropsophus elegans* (Wied, 1824)
- *Dendropsophus elianeae* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 2000)
- *Dendropsophus frosti* Motta, Castroviejo-Fisher, Venegas, Orrico, & Padial, 2012
- *Dendropsophus gaucheri* (Lescure & Marty, 2000)
- *Dendropsophus giesleri* (Mertens, 1950)
- *Dendropsophus goughi* (Boulenger, 1911)
- *Dendropsophus haddadi* (Bastos & Pombal, 1996)
- *Dendropsophus haraldschultzi* (Bokermann, 1962)
- *Dendropsophus joannae* (Köhler & Lötters, 2001)
- *Dendropsophus kamagarini* Rivadeneira, Venegas & Ron, 2018
- *Dendropsophus leali* (Bokermann, 1964)
- *Dendropsophus leucophyllatus* (Beireis, 1783)
- *Dendropsophus limai* (Bokermann, 1962)
- *Dendropsophus mapinguari* Peloso, Orrico, Haddad, Lima-Filho & Sturaro, 2016
- *Dendropsophus marmoratus* (Laurenti, 1768)
- *Dendropsophus melanargyreus* (Cope, 1887)
- *Dendropsophus meridianus* (Lutz, 1954)
- *Dendropsophus microcephalus* (Cope, 1886)
- *Dendropsophus microps* (Peter, 1872)
- *Dendropsophus minimus* (Ahl, 1933)
- *Dendropsophus minusculus* (Rivero, 1971)
- *Dendropsophus minutus* (Peters, 1872)
- *Dendropsophus miyatai* (Vigle & Goberdhan-Vigle, 1990)
- *Dendropsophus nahdereri* (Lutz & Bokermann, 1963)
- *Dendropsophus nanus* (Boulenger, 1889)
- *Dendropsophus nekronastes* Dias, Haddad, Argôlo & Orrico, 2017
- *Dendropsophus novaisi* (Bokermann, 1968)
- *Dendropsophus oliveirai* (Bokermann, 1963)
- *Dendropsophus ozyyi* Orrico, Peloso, Sturaro, Silva, Neckel-Oliveira, Gordo, Faivovich & Haddad, 2014
- *Dendropsophus parviceps* (Boulenger, 1882)
- *Dendropsophus pauiniensis* (Heyer, 1977)
- *Dendropsophus pseudomeridianus* (Cruz, Caramaschi & Dias, 2000)
- *Dendropsophus reichlei* Moravec, Aparicio, Guerrero-Reinhard, Calderon & Köhler, 2008
- *Dendropsophus reticulatus* (Jiménez de la Espada, 1870)
- *Dendropsophus rhodopeplus* (Günther, 1858)
- *Dendropsophus riveroi* (Cochran & Goin, 1970)
- *Dendropsophus rossalleni* (Goin, 1959)
- *Dendropsophus rubicundulus* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)
- *Dendropsophus ruschii* (Weygoldt & Peixoto, 1987)
- *Dendropsophus salli* Jungfer, Reichle & Piskurek, 2010
- *Dendropsophus sanborni* (Schmidt, 1944)
- *Dendropsophus sarayacuensis* (Shreve, 1935)
- *Dendropsophus schubarti* (Bokermann, 1963)
- *Dendropsophus seniculus* (Cope, 1868)
- *Dendropsophus shiwiarum* (Ortega-Andrade & Ron, 2013)
- *Dendropsophus soaresi* (Caramaschi & Jim, 1983)
- *Dendropsophus studerae* (Carvalho-e-Silva, Carvalho-e-Silva & Izecksohn, 2003)
- *Dendropsophus tapacurensis* Oliveira, Magalhães, Teixeira, Moura, Porto, Guimarães, Giaretta & Tinôco, 2021
- *Dendropsophus timbeba* (Martins & Cardoso, 1987)
- *Dendropsophus tintinnabulum* (Melin, 1941)
- *Dendropsophus triangulum* (Günther, 1869)
- *Dendropsophus tritaeniatus* (Bokermann, 1965)
- *Dendropsophus walfordi* (Bokermann, 1962)
- *Dendropsophus werneri* (Cochran, 1952)

- *Dendropsophus xapuriensis* (Martins & Cardoso, 1987)
- *Xenohyla eugenioi* Caramaschi, 1998
- *Xenohyla truncata* (Izecksohn, 1959)

Lophyohylini (8/56)

- *Corythomantis botoque* Marques, Haddad & Garda, 2021
- *Corythomantis greeningi* Boulenger, 1896
- *Dryaderces inframaculata* (Boulenger, 1882)
- *Itapotihyla langsdorffii* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)
- *Nyctimantis arapapa* (Pimenta, Napoli & Haddad, 2009)
- *Nyctimantis bokermanni* (Pombal, 1993)
- *Nyctimantis brunoi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)
- *Nyctimantis diadorim* Brandão, Queiroz, Ferreira, Álvares, Blotto, Garda, Gedraite, Santoro, Faivovich, 2024
- *Nyctimantis galeata* Pombal, Menezes, Fontes, Nunes, Rocha & Van Sluys, 2012
- *Nyctimantis pomba* (Assis, Santana, Silva, Quintela & Feio, 2013)
- *Osteocephalus buckleyi* (Boulenger, 1882)
- *Osteocephalus cabrerai* (Cochran & Goin, 1970)
- *Osteocephalus camufatus* Jungfer, Verdade, Faivovich & Rodrigues, 2016
- *Osteocephalus castaneicola* Moravec, Aparicio, Guerrero-Reinhard, Calderón, Jungfer & Gvoždík, 2009
- *Osteocephalus deridens* Jungfer, Ron, Seipp & Almendariz, 2000
- *Osteocephalus helenae* (Ruthven, 1919)
- *Osteocephalus heyeri* Lynch, 2002
- *Osteocephalus leprieurii* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)
- *Osteocephalus melanops* Melo-Sampaio, Ferrão & Moraes, 2021
- *Osteocephalus oophagus* Jungfer & Schiesari, 1995
- *Osteocephalus planiceps* Cope, 1874
- *Osteocephalus subtilis* Martins & Cardoso, 1987
- *Osteocephalus taurinus* Steindachner, 1862
- *Osteocephalus vilarsi* (Melin, 1941)
- *Osteocephalus yasuni* Ron & Pramuk, 1999
- *Phyllodytes acuminatus* Bokermann, 1966
- *Phyllodytes amadoi* Voros, Dias & Solé, 2017
- *Phyllodytes brevirostris* Peixoto & Cruz, 1988
- *Phyllodytes edelmi* Peixoto, Caramaschi & Freire, 2003
- *Phyllodytes gyrinaethes* Peixoto, Caramaschi & Freire, 2003
- *Phyllodytes iuna* Santos, Roseno, Solé & Dias, 2023
- *Phyllodytes kautskyi* Peixoto & Cruz, 1988
- *Phyllodytes luteolus* (Wied, 1824)
- *Phyllodytes maculosus* Cruz, Feio & Cardoso, 2007
- *Phyllodytes magnus* Dias, Novaes-e-Fagundes, Neto, Zina, Garcia, Recoder, Dal Vechio, Rodrigues & Solé, 2020
- *Phyllodytes megatympanum* Marciano, Lantyer-Silva & Solé, 2017
- *Phyllodytes melanomystax* Caramaschi, Silva & Britto-Pereira, 1992
- *Phyllodytes praeceptor* Orrico, Dias & Marciano, 2018
- *Phyllodytes punctatus* Caramaschi & Peixoto, 2004
- *Phyllodytes tuberculatus* Bokermann, 1966
- *Phyllodytes wuchereri* (Peters, 1873)
- *Tepuihyla shushupe* Ron, Venegas, Ortega-Andrade, Gagliardi-Urrutia & Salerno, 2016
- *Trachycephalus atlas* Bokermann, 1966
- *Trachycephalus coriaceus* (Peters, 1867)
- *Trachycephalus cunauaru* Gordo, Toledo, Suárez, Kawashita-Ribeiro, Ávila, Morais & Nunes, 2013
- *Trachycephalus dibernardoi* Kwet & Solé, 2008
- *Trachycephalus hadroceps* (Duellman & Hoogmoed, 1992)
- *Trachycephalus helioi* Nunes, Suárez, Gordo & Pombal, 2013
- *Trachycephalus imitatrix* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
- *Trachycephalus lepidus* (Pombal, Haddad & Cruz, 2003)
- *Trachycephalus mambaiensis* Cintra, Silva, Silva-Jr, Garcia & Zaher, 2009
- *Trachycephalus mesophaeus* (Hensel, 1867)
- *Trachycephalus nigromaculatus* Tschudi, 1838
- *Trachycephalus resinifictrix* (Goeldi, 1907)
- *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- *Trachycephalus venezolanus* (Mertens, 1950)

Pseudini (2/12)

- *Pseudis bolbodactyla* Lutz, 1925
- *Pseudis boliviana* (Gallardo, 1961)
- *Pseudis caraya* (Gallardo, 1964)
- *Pseudis cardosoi* Kwet, 2000
- *Pseudis fusca* Garman, 1883
- *Pseudis laevis* Parker, 1935

- Pseudis limellum* (Cope, 1862)
- Pseudis minuta* Günther, 1858
- Pseudis paradoxa* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Pseudis platensis* Gallardo, 1961
- Pseudis tocantins* Caramaschi & Cruz, 1998
- Scarthyla goinorum* (Bokermann, 1962)

- Scinaxini (3/118)**
- Ololygon agilis* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1983)
- Ololygon albicans* (Bokermann, 1967)
- Ololygon alcatraz* (Lutz, 1973)
- Ololygon angrensis* (Lutz, 1973)
- Ololygon arduoua* (Peixoto, 2002)
- Ololygon argyreornata* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
- Ololygon ariadne* (Lutz, 1973)
- Ololygon aromothyella* (Faivovich, 2005)
- Ololygon atrata* (Peixoto, 1989)
- Ololygon belloni* (Faivovich, Gasparini & Haddad, 2010)
- Ololygon berthae* (Barrio, 1962)
- Ololygon brieni* (Witte, 1930)
- Ololygon caissara* (Lourenco, Zina, Catroli, Kasahara, Faivovich & Haddad, 2016)
- Ololygon canastrensis* (Cardoso & Haddad, 1982)
- Ololygon cardosoi* Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 1991
- Ololygon carnevallii* Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989
- Ololygon catharinae* (Boulenger, 1888)
- Ololygon centralis* (Pombal & Bastos, 1996)
- Ololygon cosenzai* (Lacerda, Peixoto & Feio, 2012)
- Ololygon faivovichii* (Brasileiro, Oyamaguchi & Haddad, 2007)
- Ololygon feioi* (Lourenço, Lacerda, Cruz, Nascimento & Pombal, 2020)
- Ololygon flavoguttata* (Lutz & Lutz, 1939)
- Ololygon garibaldiae* (Lourenço, Lingnau, Haddad & Faivovich, 2019)
- Ololygon goya* (Andrade, Santos, Rocha, Pombal & Vaz-Silva, 2018)
- Ololygon heyeri* Peixoto & Weygoldt, 1987
- Ololygon hiemalis* (Haddad & Pombal, 1987)
- Ololygon humilis* (Lutz & Lutz, 1954)
- Ololygon insperata* (Silva & Alves-Silva, 2011)
- Ololygon jureia* (Pombal & Gordo, 1991)
- Ololygon kautskyi* (Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 1991)
- Ololygon littoralis* (Pombal & Gordo, 1991)
- Ololygon littorea* Peixoto, 1988
- Ololygon longilinea* (Lutz, 1968)
- Ololygon luizotavioi* Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989
- Ololygon machadoi* (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973)
- Ololygon melanodactyla* (Lourenco, Luna & Pombal, 2014)
- Ololygon melloi* Peixoto, 1989
- Ololygon muriciensis* (Cruz, Nunes & Lima, 2011)
- Ololygon obtriangulata* (Lutz, 1973)
- Ololygon paracatu* Carvalho, Valencia-Zuleta, Araujo-Vieira, Faivovich, Maciel, & Brandão, 2026
- Ololygon paulofreirei* Roberto, Ávila, Lima & Santos, 2025
- Ololygon peixotoi* (Brasileiro, Haddad, Sawaya & Martins, 2007)
- Ololygon perpusilla* (Lutz & Lutz, 1939)
- Ololygon pixinguinha* (Lacerda, Ferreira, Araujo-Vieira, Zocca, & Lourenço, 2021) (Fig. 21)
- Ololygon pombali* (Lourenco, Carvalho, Baêta, Pezzuti & Leite, 2013)
- Ololygon ranki* (Andrade & Cardoso, 1987)
- Ololygon rizibilis* (Bokermann, 1964)
- Ololygon skaios* (Pombal, Carvalho, Canelas & Bastos, 2010)
- Ololygon skuki* (Lima, Cruz & Azevedo, 2011)
- Ololygon strigilata* (Spix, 1824)
- Ololygon trapicheiroi* (Lutz & Lutz, 1954)
- Ololygon tripui* (Lourenco, Nascimento & Pires, 2010)
- Ololygon tupinamba* (Silva & Alves-Silva, 2008)
- Ololygon v-signata* (Lutz, 1968)
- Scinax acuminatus* (Cope, 1862)
- Scinax albertinae* Ferrão, Moravec, Ferreira, Moraes & Hanken, 2022
- Scinax alter* (Lutz, 1973)
- Scinax auratus* (Wied, 1821)
- Scinax boesemani* (Goin, 1966)
- Scinax cabralensis* Drummond, Baêta & Pires, 2007
- Scinax caldarum* (Lutz, 1968)
- Scinax chiquitanus* (De la Riva, 1990)
- Scinax coerulea* (Spix, 1824)
- Scinax constrictus* Lima, Bastos & Giaretta, 2004

- *Scinax cretatus* Nunes & Pombal, 2011
 - *Scinax crospeospilus* (Lutz, 1925)
 - *Scinax cruentomma* (Duellman, 1972)
 - *Scinax curicica* Pugliesse, Pombal & Sazima, 2004
 - *Scinax cuspidatus* (Lutz, 1925)
 - *Scinax dolloi* (Werner, 1903)
 - *Scinax duartei* (Lutz, 1951)
 - *Scinax eurydice* (Bokermann, 1968)
 - *Scinax exiguus* (Duellman, 1986)
 - *Scinax funereus* (Cope, 1874)
 - *Scinax fuscomarginatus* (Lutz, 1925)
 - *Scinax fuscovarius* (Lutz, 1925)
 - *Scinax garbei* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
 - *Scinax granulatus* (Peters, 1871)
 - *Scinax haddadorum* Araujo-Vieira, Valdujo & Faivovich, 2016
 - *Scinax hayii* (Barbour, 1909)
 - *Scinax ictericus* Duellman & Wiens, 1993
 - *Scinax imbegue* Nunes, Kwet & Pombal, 2012
 - *Scinax iquitum* Moravec, Tuanama, Pérez-Peña & Lehr, 2009
 - *Scinax jolyi* Lescure & Marty, 2000
 - *Scinax juncae* Nunes & Pombal, 2010
 - *Scinax juruena* Ferrão, Hanken, Oda, Campião, Penhacek, Anjos & Rodrigues, 2024
 - *Scinax kennedyi* (Pyburn, 1973)
 - *Scinax lindsayi* Pyburn, 1992
 - *Scinax madeirae* (Bokermann, 1964)
 - *Scinax maracaya* (Cardoso & Sazima, 1980)
 - *Scinax montivagus* Juncá, Napoli, Nunes, Mercedes & Abreu, 2015
 - *Scinax nasicus* (Cope, 1862)
 - *Scinax nebulosus* (Spix, 1824)
 - *Scinax onca* Ferrão, Moravec, Fraga, Almeida, Kaefer & Lima, 2017
 - *Scinax pachycrus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)
 - *Scinax pedromedinae* (Henle, 1991)
 - *Scinax perereca* Pombal, Haddad & Kasahara, 1995
 - *Scinax proboscideus* (Brongersma, 1933)
 - *Scinax ritaleae* Marinho, Faivovich, Haddad & Araujo-Vieira, 2024
 - *Scinax rogerioi* Pugliesi, Baêta & Pombal, 2009
 - *Scinax rossaferesae* Conte, Araujo-Vieira, Crivellari & Berneck, 2016
 - *Scinax rostratus* (Peter, 1863)
 - *Scinax ruber* (Laurenti, 1768)
 - *Scinax ruberoculatus* Ferrão, Fraga, Moravec, Kaefer & Lima, 2018
 - *Scinax rupestris* Araujo-Vieira, Brandão & Faria, 2015
 - *Scinax sateremawe* Sturaro & Peloso, 2014
 - *Scinax similis* (Cochran, 1952)
 - *Scinax squalirostris* (Lutz, 1925)
 - *Scinax strussmannae* Ferrão, Moravec, Kaefer, Fraga & Lima, 2018
 - *Scinax tigrinus* Nunes, Carvalho & Pereira, 2010
 - *Scinax tropicalia* Novaes-e-Fagundes, Araujo-Vieira, Entiauspe-Neto, Roberto, Orrico, Solé, Haddad & Loebmann, 2021
 - *Scinax tymbamirim* Nunes, Kwet & Pombal, 2012
 - *Scinax villasboasi* Brusquetti, Jansen, Barrio-Amorós, Segalla & Haddad, 2014
 - *Scinax x-signatus* (Spix, 1824)
 - *Julianus camposseabrai* (Bokermann, 1968)
 - *Julianus fontanarrosai* (Baldo, Araujo-Vieira, Cardozo, Borteiro, Leal, Pereyra, Kolenc, Lyra, Garcia, Haddad & Faivovich, 2019)
 - *Julianus pinimus* (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973)
 - *Julianus uruguayus* (Schmidt, 1944)
- ### Sphaenorhynchini (2/15)
- *Gabohyla pauloalvini* Bokermann, 1973
 - *Sphaenorhynchus botocudo* Caramaschi, Almeida & Gasparini, 2009
 - *Sphaenorhynchus bromelicola* Bokermann, 1966
 - *Sphaenorhynchus cammaeus* Roberto, Araujo-Vieira, Carvalho-e-Silva & Ávila, 2017
 - *Sphaenorhynchus canga* Araujo-Vieira, Lacerda, Pezzuti, Assis & Cruz, 2015
 - *Sphaenorhynchus caramaschii* Toledo, Garcia, Lingnau & Haddad, 2007
 - *Sphaenorhynchus carneus* (Cope, 1868)
 - *Sphaenorhynchus dorisae* (Goin, 1957)
 - *Sphaenorhynchus lacteus* (Daudin, 1800)

- Sphaenorhynchus mirim* Caramaschi, Almeida & Gasparini, 2009
- Sphaenorhynchus palustris* Bokermann, 1966
- Sphaenorhynchus planicola* (Lutz & Lutz, 1938)
- Sphaenorhynchus platycephalus* (Werner, 1894)
- Sphaenorhynchus prasinus* Bokermann, 1973
- Sphaenorhynchus surdus* (Cochran, 1953)

Hylodidae (4/48)

- Crossodactylus boulengeri* (De Witte, 1930)
- Crossodactylus caramaschii* Bastos & Pombal, 1995
- Crossodactylus cyclospinus* Nascimento, Cruz & Feio, 2005
- Crossodactylus dantei* Carcerelli & Caramaschi, 1993
- Crossodactylus dispar* Lutz, 1925
- Crossodactylus franciscanus* Pimenta, Caramaschi & Cruz, 2015
- Crossodactylus gaudichaudii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841
- Crossodactylus grandis* Lutz, 1951
- Crossodactylus lutzorum* Carcerelli & Caramaschi, 1993
- Crossodactylus schmidti* Gallardo, 1961
- Crossodactylus timbuhy* Pimenta, Cruz & Caramaschi, 2014
- Crossodactylus trachystomus* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)
- Crossodactylus werneri* Pimenta, Cruz & Caramaschi, 2014
- Hylodes amnicola* Pombal, Feio & Haddad, 2002
- Hylodes asper* (Müller, 1924)
- Hylodes babax* Heyer, 1982
- Hylodes caete* Malagoli, de Sá, Canedo & Haddad, 2017
- Hylodes cardosoi* Lingnau, Canedo & Pombal, 2008
- Hylodes charadranaetes* Heyer & Cocroft, 1986
- Hylodes dactylocinus* Pavan, Narvaes & Rodrigues, 2001
- Hylodes fredii* Canedo & Pombal, 2007
- Hylodes glaber* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
- Hylodes heyeri* Haddad, Pombal & Bastos, 1996
- Hylodes japi* de Sá, Canedo, Lyra & Haddad, 2015
- Hylodes lateristrigatus* (Baumann, 1912)
- Hylodes magalhaesi* (Bokermann, 1964)
- Hylodes meridionalis* (Mertens, 1927)
- Hylodes mertensi* (Bokermann, 1956)
- Hylodes nasus* (Lichtenstein, 1823)
- Hylodes ornatus* (Bokermann, 1967)
- Hylodes otavioi* Sazima & Bokermann, 1983
- Hylodes perere* Silva & Benmaman, 2008
- Hylodes perplicatus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
- Hylodes phyllodes* Heyer & Cocroft, 1986
- Hylodes pipilans* Canedo & Pombal, 2007
- Hylodes regius* Gouvea, 1979
- Hylodes sazimai* Haddad & Pombal, 1995
- Hylodes uai* Nascimento, Pombal & Haddad, 2001
- Hylodes vanzolinii* Heyer, 1982
- Megaelosia goeldii* (Baumann, 1912)
- Phantasmarana apuana* (Pombal, Prado & Canedo, 2003)
- Phantasmarana bocainensis* (Giaretta, Bokermann & Haddad, 1993)
- Phantasmarana boticariana* (Giaretta & Aguiar, 1998)
- Phantasmarana curucutuensis* de Sá, Condez, Lyra, Haddad & Malagoli 2022 (Fig. 2J)
- Phantasmarana jordanensis* (Heyer, 1983)
- Phantasmarana lutzae* (Izecksohn & Gouvea, 1985)
- Phantasmarana massarti* (De Witte, 1930)
- Phantasmarana tamuia* de Sá, Condez, Lyra, Haddad & Malagoli 2022 (Fig. 3A)

Leptodactylidae (13/193)

Leiuperinae (5/78)

- Edalorhina perezii* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870
- Engystomops freibergeri* (Donoso-Barros, 1969)
- Engystomops petersi* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872
- Physalaemus aguirrei* Bokermann, 1966
- Physalaemus albifrons* (Spix, 1824)
- Physalaemus albonotatus* (Steindachner, 1864)
- Physalaemus angrensis* Weber, Gonzaga & Carvalho-e-Silva, 2006 “2005”
- Physalaemus araxa* Leal, Zornosa-Torres, Augusto-Alves, Dena, Pezzuti, Leite, Lourenço, Garcia & Toledo 2021 (Fig. 3B)
- Physalaemus atim* Brasileiro & Haddad, 2015
- Physalaemus atlanticus* Haddad & Sazima, 2004
- Physalaemus barrioi* Bokermann, 1967
- Physalaemus biligonigerus* (Cope, 1861)
- Physalaemus bokermanni* Cardoso & Haddad, 1985
- Physalaemus caete* Pombal & Madureira, 1997
- Physalaemus camacan* Pimenta, Cruz & Silvano, 2005
- Physalaemus carrizorum* Cardozo & Pereyra, 2018

- Physalaemus centralis* Bokermann, 1962
- Physalaemus cicada* Bokermann, 1966
- Physalaemus claptoni* Leal, Leite, Costa, Nascimento, Lourenço & Garcia, 2020
- Physalaemus crombiei* Heyer & Wolf, 1989
- Physalaemus cuvieri* Fitzinger, 1826
- Physalaemus deimaticus* Sazima & Caramaschi, 1988
- Physalaemus ephippifer* (Steindachner, 1864)
- Physalaemus erikae* Cruz & Pimenta, 2004
- Physalaemus erythros* Caramaschi, Feio & Guimaraes-Neto, 2003
- Physalaemus evangelistai* Bokermann, 1967
- Physalaemus feioi* Cassini, Cruz & Caramaschi, 2010
- Physalaemus gracilis* (Boulenger, 1883)
- Physalaemus henselii* (Peters, 1872)
- Physalaemus insperatus* Cruz, Cassini & Caramaschi, 2008
- Physalaemus irroratus* Cruz, Nascimento & Feio, 2007
- Physalaemus jordanensis* Bokermann, 1967
- Physalaemus kroyeri* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)
- Physalaemus lateristriga* (Steindachner, 1864)
- Physalaemus lisei* Braun & Braun, 1977
- Physalaemus maculiventris* (Lutz, 1925)
- Physalaemus marmoratus* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)
- Physalaemus maximus* Feio, Pombal & Caramaschi, 1999
- Physalaemus moreirae* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)
- Physalaemus nanus* (Boulenger, 1888)
- Physalaemus nattereri* (Steindachner, 1863)
- Physalaemus obtectus* Bokermann, 1966
- Physalaemus olfersii* (Lichtenstein & Martens, 1856)
- Physalaemus orophilus* Cassini, Cruz & Caramaschi, 2010
- Physalaemus riograndensis* Milstead, 1960
- Physalaemus rupestris* Caramaschi, Carcerelli & Feio, 1991
- Physalaemus signifer* (Girard, 1853)
- Physalaemus soaresi* Izecksohn, 1965
- Physalaemus spiniger* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
- Pleurodema alium* Maciel & Nunes, 2010
- Pleurodema bibroni* Tschudi, 1838
- Pleurodema brachyops* (Cope, 1869)
- Pleurodema diplolister* (Peters, 1870)
- Pseudopaludicola ameghini* (Cope, 1887)
- Pseudopaludicola atragula* Pansonato, Mudrek, Veiga-Menocello, Rossa-Feres, Martins & Strüssmann, 2014
- Pseudopaludicola boliviana* Parker, 1927
- Pseudopaludicola canga* Giaretta & Kokubum, 2003
- Pseudopaludicola ceratophyes* Rivero & Serna, 1984
- Pseudopaludicola chimaera* Silva, Haga, Neto, Dantas, Varago, Garda, Kohlsdorf & Andrade, 2024 (Fig. 3C)
- Pseudopaludicola coracoralinae* Andrade, Haga, Lyra, Carvalho, Haddad, Giaretta & Toledo, 2020
- Pseudopaludicola facureae* Andrade & Carvalho, 2013
- Pseudopaludicola falcipes* (Hensel, 1867)
- Pseudopaludicola florencei* Andrade, Haga, Lyra, Leite, Kwet, Haddad, Toledo & Giaretta, 2018
- Pseudopaludicola giarettai* Carvalho, 2012
- Pseudopaludicola hyleaustralis* Pansonato, Morais, Ávila, Kawashita-Ribeiro, Strüssmann & Martin, 2013
- Pseudopaludicola ibisoroca* Pansonato, Veiga-Menocello, Mudrek, Jansen, Recco-Pimentel, Martins & Strüssmann, 2016
- Pseudopaludicola jaredi* Andrade, Magalhães, Nunes-de-Almeida, Veiga-Menocello, Santana, Garda, Loebmann, Recco-Pimentel, Giaretta & Toledo, 2016
- Pseudopaludicola javae* Silva, Andrade, Painkow Neto, Dantas, Haga & Garda, 2023 (Fig. 3D)
- Pseudopaludicola jazmynmcdonaldae* Andrade, Silva, Koroiva, Fadel & Santana, 2019
- Pseudopaludicola matuta* Andrade, Haga, Lyra, Carvalho, Haddad, Giaretta & Toledo, 2018
- Pseudopaludicola mineira* Lobo, 1994
- Pseudopaludicola motorzinho* Pansonato, Veiga-Menocello, Mudrek, Jansen, Recco-Pimentel, Martins & Strüssmann, 2016
- Pseudopaludicola murundu* Toledo, Siqueira, Duarte, Veiga-Menocello, Recco-Pimentel & Haddad, 2010
- Pseudopaludicola mystacalis* (Cope, 1887)
- Pseudopaludicola pocoto* Magalhães, Loebmann, Kokubum, Haddad & Garda, 2014
- Pseudopaludicola restinga* Cardozo, Baldo, Pupin, Gasparini & Haddad, 2018
- Pseudopaludicola saltica* (Cope, 1887)
- Pseudopaludicola ternetzi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937

Leptodactylinae (4/96)

- *Adenomera ajurauna* (Berneck, Costa & Garcia, 2008)
- *Adenomera albarena* Martins, Mônico, Mendonça, Dantas, Souza, Hanken, Lima & Ferrão, 2024
- *Adenomera amicum* Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2021
- *Adenomera andreae* (Müller, 1923)
- *Adenomera araucaria* Kwet & Angulo, 2002
- *Adenomera aurantiaca* Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2021
- *Adenomera bokermanni* (Heyer, 1973)
- *Adenomera cantitata* Cassini, Carvalho, Taucce, Haddad & Solé, 2024
- *Adenomera chicomendesi* Carvalho, Ângulo, Kokubum, Barrera, Souza, Haddad & Giaretta, 2019
- *Adenomera cotuba* Carvalho & Giaretta, 2013
- *Adenomera diptyx* (Boettger, 1885)
- *Adenomera engelsi* Kwet, Steiner & Zillikens, 2009)
- *Adenomera glauciae* Carvalho, Simões, Gagliardi-Urrutia, Rojas-Runjaic, Haddad & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2020
- *Adenomera gridipappi* Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2021
- *Adenomera guarani* Zaracho, Lavilla, Carvalho, Motte & Basso, 2023 (Fig. 3E)
- *Adenomera heyeri* Boistel, Massary & Angulo, 2006
- *Adenomera hylaedactyla* (Cope, 1868)
- *Adenomera inopinata* Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2021
- *Adenomera juikitam* Carvalho & Giaretta, 2013
- *Adenomera kayapo* Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2021
- *Adenomera kweti* Carvalho, Cassini, Taucce & Haddad, 2019
- *Adenomera marmorata* Steindachner, 1867
- *Adenomera martinezi* (Bokermann, 1956)
- *Adenomera nana* (Müller, 1922)
- *Adenomera phonotriccus* Carvalho, Giaretta, Ângulo, Haddad & Peloso, 2019
- *Adenomera saci* Carvalho & Giaretta, 2013
- *Adenomera simonstuarti* (Angulo & Icochea, 2010)
- *Adenomera tapajonica* Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2021
- *Adenomera thomei* (Almeida & Angulo, 2006)
- *Hydrolaetare caparu* Jansen, Gonzalez-álvares & Kohler, 2007
- *Hydrolaetare dantasi* (Bokermann, 1959)
- *Hydrolaetare schmidtii* (Cochran & Goin, 1959)
- *Leptodactylus avivoca* Carvalho, Seger, Magalhães, Lourenço & Haddad, 2021
- *Leptodactylus barrioi* Silva, Magalhães, Thomassen, Leite, Garda, Brandão, Haddad, Giaretta & Carvalho, 2020
- *Leptodactylus bolivianus* Boulenger, 1898
- *Leptodactylus brevipes* Cope, 1887
- *Leptodactylus bufonius* Boulenger, 1894
- *Leptodactylus caatingae* Heyer & Juncá, 2003
- *Leptodactylus camaquara* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978
- *Leptodactylus cunicularius* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978
- *Leptodactylus cupreus* Caramaschi, Feio & São-Pedro, 2008
- *Leptodactylus didymus* Heyer, García-Lopez & Cardoso, 1996
- *Leptodactylus diedrus* Heyer, 1994
- *Leptodactylus discodactylus* Boulenger, 1884
- *Leptodactylus elenae* Heyer, 1978
- *Leptodactylus flavopictus* Lutz, 1926
- *Leptodactylus fremitus* Carvalho, Fouquet, Lyra, Giaretta, Costa-Campos, Rodrigues, Haddad & Ron, 2022
- *Leptodactylus furnarius* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978
- *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Schneider, 1799)
- *Leptodactylus gracilis* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)
- *Leptodactylus gualambensis* Gallardo, 1964
- *Leptodactylus guianensis* Heyer & de Sá, 2011
- *Leptodactylus hylodes* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)
- *Leptodactylus intermedius* Lutz, 1930
- *Leptodactylus jolyi* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978
- *Leptodactylus kilombo* Silva, Magalhães, Thomassen, Leite, Garda, Brandão, Haddad, Giaretta & Carvalho, 2020

- Leptodactylus knudseni* Heyer, 1972
 - Leptodactylus labyrinthicus* (Spix, 1824)
 - Leptodactylus latinasus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875
 - Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815)
 - Leptodactylus lauramiriamae* Heyer & Crombie, 2005
 - Leptodactylus leptodactyloides* (Andersson, 1945)
 - Leptodactylus longirostris* Boulenger, 1882
 - Leptodactylus luctator* (Hudson, 1892)
 - Leptodactylus macrosternum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926
 - Leptodactylus marambaiae* Izecksohn, 1976
 - Leptodactylus myersi* Heyer, 1995
 - Leptodactylus mystaceus* (Spix, 1824)
 - Leptodactylus mystacinus* (Burmeister, 1861)
 - Leptodactylus natalensis* Lutz, 1930
 - Leptodactylus notoaktites* Heyer, 1978
 - Leptodactylus ochraceus* Lutz, 1930
 - Leptodactylus oreomantis* Carvalho, Leite & Pezzuti, 2013
 - Leptodactylus paraensis* Heyer, 2005
 - Leptodactylus paranaru* Magalhães, Lyra, Carvalho, Baldo, Brusquetti, Burella, Colli, Gehara, Giaretta, Haddad, Langone, López, Napoli, Santana, De Sá & Garda, 2020
 - Leptodactylus payaya* Magalhães, Lyra, Carvalho, Baldo, Brusquetti, Burella, Colli, Gehara, Giaretta, Haddad, Langone, López, Napoli, Santana, De Sá & Garda, 2020
 - Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768)
 - Leptodactylus petersii* (Steindachner, 1864)
 - Leptodactylus plaumanni* Ahl, 1936
 - Leptodactylus podicipinus* (Cope, 1862)
 - Leptodactylus pustulatus* (Peters, 1870)
 - Leptodactylus rhodomystax* Boulenger, 1884
 - Leptodactylus rhodonotus* (Günther, 1869)
 - Leptodactylus riveroi* Heyer & Pyburn, 1983
 - Leptodactylus sabanensis* Heyer, 1994
 - Leptodactylus spixi* Heyer, 1983
 - Leptodactylus stenodema* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875
 - Leptodactylus syphax* Bokermann, 1969
 - Leptodactylus tapiti* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978
 - Leptodactylus troglodytes* Lutz, 1926
 - Leptodactylus validus* Garman, 1888
 - Leptodactylus vastus* Lutz, 1930
 - Leptodactylus viridis* Jim & Spirandeli-Cruz, 1973
 - Leptodactylus wagneri* (Peters, 1862)
 - Leptodactylus watu* Silva, Magalhães, Thomassen, Leite, Garda, Brandão, Haddad, Giaretta & Carvalho, 2020
 - Lithodytes lineatus* (Schneider, 1799)
- Paratelmatoibiinae (4/19)**
- Crossodactylodes alairi* Santos, Gehara, Oswald, Ferreira, Santos, Garcia, Zamudio, Haddad & Magalhães, 2025
 - Crossodactylodes bokermanni* Peixoto, 1983
 - Crossodactylodes itambe* Barata, Santos, Leite & Garcia, 2013
 - Crossodactylodes izecksohni* Peixoto, 1983
 - Crossodactylodes pinto* Cochran, 1938
 - Crossodactylodes septentrionalis* Teixeira, Recoder, Amaro, Damasceno, Cassimiro & Rodrigues, 2013
 - Crossodactylodes serranegra* Santos, Pinheiro, Garcia, Griffiths, Haddad & Barata, 2023
 - Crossodactylodes teixeirai* Ferreira, Zocca, Carvalho, Haddad, & Santos, 2023
 - Paratelmatoibius cardosoi* Pombal & Haddad, 1999
 - Paratelmatoibius gaigeae* (Cochran, 1938)
 - Paratelmatoibius lutzii* Lutz & Carvalho, 1958
 - Paratelmatoibius mantiqueira* Pombal & Haddad, 1999
 - Paratelmatoibius poecilogaster* Giaretta & Castanho, 1990
 - Paratelmatoibius segallai* Santos, Oliveira, Carvalho, Zaidan, Silva, Berneck, & Garcia, 2019
 - Paratelmatoibius stellaris* Santos, Vilela, Carvalho, Silva, Rodrigues, Garcia, Carvalho & Haddad, 2025
 - Paratelmatoibius yepiranga* Garcia, Berneck & Costa, 2009
 - Rupirana cardosoi* Heyer, 1999
 - Rupirana kaatinga* Mângia, Amaral, Müller & Santana, 2026 (Fig. 3F)
 - Scythrophrys sawayae* (Cochran, 1953)
- Microhylidae (11/54)**
- Adelastinae (1/1)**
- Adelastes hylonomos* Zweifel, 1986
- Gastrophryninae (9/50)**
- Arcovomer passarellii* Carvalho, 1954

- *Chiasmocleis alagoana* Cruz, Caramaschi & Freire, 1999
 - *Chiasmocleis albopunctata* (Boettger, 1885)
 - *Chiasmocleis altomontana* Forlani, Tonini, Cruz, Zaher & de Sá, 2017
 - *Chiasmocleis antenori* (Walker, 1973)
 - *Chiasmocleis atlantica* Cruz, Caramaschi & Izecksohn, 1997
 - *Chiasmocleis avilapiresae* Peloso & Sturaro 2008
 - *Chiasmocleis bassleri* Dunn, 1949
 - *Chiasmocleis bicegoi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920
 - *Chiasmocleis capixaba* Cruz, Caramaschi & Izecksohn, 1997
 - *Chiasmocleis centralis* Bokermann, 1952
 - *Chiasmocleis cordeiroi* Caramaschi & Pimenta, 2003
 - *Chiasmocleis crucis* Caramaschi & Pimenta, 2003
 - *Chiasmocleis gnoma* Canedo, Dixo & Pombal, 2004
 - *Chiasmocleis hudsoni* Parker, 1940
 - *Chiasmocleis jacki* Fouquet, Rodrigues & Peloso, 2022
 - *Chiasmocleis lacrimae* Peloso, Sturaro, Forlani, Gaucher, Motta & Wheeler, 2014
 - *Chiasmocleis leucosticta* (Boulenger, 1888)
 - *Chiasmocleis mantiqueira* Cruz, Feio & Cassini, 2007
 - *Chiasmocleis mehelyi* Caramaschi & Cruz, 1997
 - *Chiasmocleis migueli* Forlani, Tonini, Cruz, Zaher & de Sá, 2017
 - *Chiasmocleis papachibe* Peloso, Sturaro, Forlani, Gaucher, Motta & Wheeler, 2014
 - *Chiasmocleis quilombola* Tonini, Forlani & Sá, 2014
 - *Chiasmocleis royi* Peloso, Sturaro, Forlani, Gaucher, Motta & Wheeler, 2014
 - *Chiasmocleis sapiranga* Cruz, Caramaschi & Napoli, 2007
 - *Chiasmocleis schubarti* Bokermann, 1952
 - *Chiasmocleis shudikarensis* Dunn, 1949
 - *Chiasmocleis superciliarba* Morales & McDiarmid, 2009
 - *Chiasmocleis tridactyla* (Duellman & Mendelson, 1995)
 - *Chiasmocleis ventrimaculata* (Andersson, 1945)
 - *Chiasmocleis veracruz* Forlani, Tonini, Cruz, Zaher & de Sá, 2017
 - *Ctenophryne geayi* Mocquard, 1904
 - *Dasypops schirchi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1924
 - *Dermatonotus muelleri* (Boettger, 1885)
 - *Elachistocleis bicolor* (Valenciennes in Guérin-Ménéville, 1838)
 - *Elachistocleis cesarii* (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920)
 - *Elachistocleis corumbaensis* Piva, Caramaschi & Albuquerque, 2017
 - *Elachistocleis erythrogaster* Kwet & Di-Bernardo, 1998
 - *Elachistocleis helianneae* Caramaschi, 2010
 - *Elachistocleis magna* Toledo, 2010
 - *Elachistocleis muiraquitana* Nunes-de-Almeida & Toledo, 2012
 - *Elachistocleis piauiensis* Caramaschi & Jim, 1983
 - *Elachistocleis surinamensis* (Daudin, 1802)
 - *Hamptophryne alios* (Wild, 1995)
 - *Hamptophryne boliviana* (Parker, 1927)
 - *Myersiella microps* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)
 - *Stereocyclops histrio* (Carvalho, 1954)
 - *Stereocyclops incrassatus* Cope, 1870
 - *Stereocyclops palmipes* Caramaschi, Salles & Cruz, 2012
 - *Stereocyclops parkeri* (Wettstein, 1934)
- Otophryninae (1/3)**
- *Synapturanus ajuricaba* Fouquet, Leblanc, Fabre, Rodrigues, Menin, Courtois, Dewynter, Hölting, Ernst, Peloso & Kok, 2021
 - *Synapturanus mirandaribeiroi* Nelson & Lescure, 1975
 - *Synapturanus zombie* Fouquet, Leblanc, Fabre, Rodrigues, Menin, Courtois, Dewynter, Hölting, Ernst, Peloso & Kok, 2021
- Neblinaphrynidae (1/2)**
- *Neblinaphryne imeri* Fouquet, Moraes, Recoder, Camacho, Ghellere, Barutel & Rodrigues, 2024
 - *Neblinaphryne mayeri* Fouquet, Kok, Recoder, Prates, Camacho, Marques-Souza, Ghellere, McDiarmid & Rodrigues 2024
- Odontophrynidae (3/52)**
- *Macrogenioglottus alipioi* Carvalho, 1946
 - *Odontophrynus asper* (Philippi, 1902)
 - *Odontophrynus carvalhoi* Savage & Cei, 1965
 - *Odontophrynus cultripes* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1861
 - *Odontophrynus juquinha* Rocha, Sena, Pezzuti, Leite, Svartman, Rosset, Baldo & Garcia, 2017
 - *Odontophrynus lavillai* Cei, 1985
 - *Odontophrynus maisuma* Rosset, 2008

- Odontophrynus monachus* Caramaschi & Napoli, 2012
 - Odontophrynus reigi* Rosset, Fadel, Guimarães, Carvalho, Ceron, Pedrozo, Serejo, Souza, Baldo & Mângia, 2021 (Fig. 3G)
 - Odontophrynus toledo* Moroti, Pedrozo, Severgnini, Augusto-Alves, Dena, Martins, Nunes & Muscat, 2022 (Fig. 3H)
 - Proceratophrys appendiculata* (Günther, 1873)
 - Proceratophrys ararype* Mângia, Koroiva, Nunes, Roberto, Ávila, Sant'Anna, Santana & Garda, 2018
 - Proceratophrys avelinoi* Mercadal-de-Barrio & Barrio, 1993
 - Proceratophrys bagnoi* Brandão, Caramaschi, Vaz-Silva & Campos, 2013
 - Proceratophrys belzebul* Dias, Amaro, Carvalho-e-Silva & Rodrigues, 2013
 - Proceratophrys bigibbosa* (Peters, 1872)
 - Proceratophrys boiei* (Wied-Neuwied, 1824)
 - Proceratophrys branti* Brandão, Caramaschi, Vaz-Silva & Campos, 2013
 - Proceratophrys brauni* Kwet & Faivovich, 2001
 - Proceratophrys carranca* Godinho, Moura, Lacerda & Feio, 2013
 - Proceratophrys concavitympanum* Giaretta, Bernarde & Kokubum, 2000
 - Proceratophrys cristiceps* (Müller, 1884)
 - Proceratophrys cururu* Eterovick & Sazima, 1998
 - Proceratophrys dibernardo* Brandão, Caramaschi, Vaz-Silva & Campos, 2013
 - Proceratophrys gladius* Mângia, Santana, Cruz & Feio, 2014
 - Proceratophrys goyana* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)
 - Proceratophrys huntingtoni* Ávila, Pansonato & Strüssmann, 2012
 - Proceratophrys itamari* Mângia, Santana, Cruz & Feio, 2014
 - Proceratophrys izecksohni* Dias, Amaro, Carvalho-e-Silva & Rodrigues, 2013
 - Proceratophrys korekore* Santana, Silva, Sant'Anna, Shepard & Mângia, 2021 (Fig. 3I)
 - Proceratophrys laticeps* Izecksohn & Peixoto, 1981
 - Proceratophrys mantiqueira* Mângia, Santana, Cruz & Feio, 2014
 - Proceratophrys melanopogon* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
 - Proceratophrys minuta* Napoli, Cruz, Abreu & Del-Grande, 2011
 - Proceratophrys moehringi* Weygoldt & Peixoto, 1985
 - Proceratophrys moratoi* (Jim & Caramaschi 1980)
 - Proceratophrys palustris* Giaretta & Sazima, 1993
 - Proceratophrys paviotii* Cruz, Prado & Izecksohn, 2005
 - Proceratophrys phyllostomus* Izecksohn, Cruz & Peixoto, 1999
 - Proceratophrys pombali* Mângia, Santana, Cruz & Feio, 2014
 - Proceratophrys redacta* Teixeira, Amaro, Recoder, Vechio & Rodrigues, 2012
 - Proceratophrys renalis* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)
 - Proceratophrys rondonae* Prado & Pombal, 2008
 - Proceratophrys rotundipalpebra* Martins & Giaretta, 2013
 - Proceratophrys salvatori* (Caramaschi, 1996)
 - Proceratophrys sanctaritae* Cruz & Napoli, 2010
 - Proceratophrys schirchi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)
 - Proceratophrys strussmannae* Ávila, Kawashita-Ribeiro & Morais, 2011
 - Proceratophrys subguttata* Izecksohn, Cruz & Peixoto, 1999
 - Proceratophrys tupinamba* Prado & Pombal, 2008
 - Proceratophrys velhochico* Mângia, Magalhães, Leite, Cavalheri & Garda, 2022 (Fig. 3J)
 - Proceratophrys vielliardi* Martins & Giaretta, 2011
- Phyllomedusidae (7/42)**
- Callimedusa atelopoides* (Duellman, Cadle & Cannatella, 1988)
 - Callimedusa tomopterna* (Cope, 1868)
 - Cruziohyla craspedopus* (Funkhouser, 1957)
 - Hylomantis aspera* Peters, 1873
 - Hylomantis granulosa* (Cruz, 1989)
 - Phasmahyla cochranae* (Bokermann, 1966)
 - Phasmahyla cruzi* Carvalho-e-Silva, Silva & Carvalho-e-Silva, 2009
 - Phasmahyla exilis* (Cruz, 1980)
 - Phasmahyla guttata* (Lutz, 1924)
 - Phasmahyla jandaia* (Bokermann & Sazima, 1978)
 - Phasmahyla lisbella* Pereira, Rocha, Folly, Silva & Santana, 2018
 - Phasmahyla spectabilis* Cruz, Feio & Nascimento, 2008
 - Phasmahyla timbo* Cruz, Napoli & Fonseca, 2008

- Phrynomedusa appendiculata* (Lutz, 1925)
- Phrynomedusa bokermanni* Cruz, 1991
- Phrynomedusa dryade* Baêta, Giasson, Pombal & Haddad, 2016
- Phrynomedusa fimbriata* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923
- Phrynomedusa marginata* (Izecksohn & Cruz, 1976)
- Phrynomedusa vanzolinii* Cruz, 1991
- Phyllomedusa bahiana* Lutz, 1925
- Phyllomedusa bicolor* (Boddaert, 1772)
- Phyllomedusa boliviana* Boulenger, 1902
- Phyllomedusa burmeisteri* Boulenger, 1882
- Phyllomedusa camba* De la Riva, 1999
- Phyllomedusa distincta* Lutz, 1950
- Phyllomedusa iheringii* Boulenger, 1885
- Phyllomedusa sauvagii* Boulenger, 1882
- Phyllomedusa tarsius* (Cope, 1868)
- Phyllomedusa tetraploidea* Pombal & Haddad, 1992
- Phyllomedusa vaillantii* Boulenger, 1882
- Pithecopus araguaeus* Haga, Andrade, Bruschi, Recco-Pimentel & Giaretta, 2017
- Pithecopus ayeaye* Lutz, 1966
- Pithecopus azureus* (Cope, 1862)
- Pithecopus centralis* (Bokermann, 1965)
- Pithecopus gonzagai* Andrade, Haga, Ferreira, Recco-Pimentel, Toledo & Bruschi, 2020
- Pithecopus hypochondrialis* (Daudin, 1800)
- Pithecopus megacephalus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)
- Pithecopus nordestinus* (Caramaschi, 2006)
- Pithecopus oreades* (Brandão, 2002)
- Pithecopus palliatus* (Peters, 1873)
- Pithecopus rohdei* (Mertens, 1926)
- Pithecopus rusticus* (Bruschi, Lucas, Garcia & Recco-Pimentel, 2016)

Pipidae (1/4)

- Pipa arrabali* Izecksohn, 1976
- Pipa carvalhoi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)
- Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Pipa snethlageae* Müller, 1914

Ranidae (2/2)

- Aquarana catesbeiana* (Shaw, 1802)
- Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824)

CAUDATA (1/5)

Plethodontidae (1/5)

Hemidactyliinae (1/5)

- Bolitoglossa altamazonica* (Cope, 1874)
- Bolitoglossa caldwella* Brcko, Hoogmoed & Neckel-Oliveira, 2013
- Bolitoglossa madeira* Brcko, Hoogmoed & Neckel-Oliveira, 2013
- Bolitoglossa paraensis* (Unterstein, 1930)
- Bolitoglossa tapajonica* Brcko, Hoogmoed & Neckel-Oliveira, 2013

GYMNOPHIONA (13/40)

Caeciliidae (2/5)

- Caecilia armata* Dunn, 1942
- Caecilia gracilis* Shaw, 1802
- Caecilia marcusii* Wake, 1985
- Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758
- Osgaecilia hypereumeces* Taylor, 1968

Rhinatreumatidae (1/4)

- Rhinatrema bivittatum* (Cuvier in Guérin-Méneville, 1829)
- Rhinatrema gilbertogili* Maciel, Sampaio, Hoogmoed & Schneider, 2018
- Rhinatrema ron* Wilkinson & Gower, 2010
- Rhinatrema uaiuai* Maciel, Sampaio, Hoogmoed & Schneider, 2018

Siphonopidae (5/18)

- Brasilotyphlus braziliensis* (Dunn, 1945)
- Brasilotyphlus dubium* Correia, Nunes, Gamble, Maciel, Marques-Souza, Fouquet, Rodrigues & Mott, 2018
- Brasilotyphlus guarantanus* Maciel, Mott & Hoogmoed, 2009
- Luetkenotyphlus brasiliensis* (Lütken, 1852)
- Luetkenotyphlus fredii* Maciel, Castro, Sturaro, Silva, Ferreira, Santos, Risse-Quaioto, Barboza, Oliveira, Sampaio & Schneider,

2019

- *Luetkenotyphlus insulanus* Ihering, 1911
- *Microcaecilia butantan* Wilkinson, Antoniazzi & Jared, 2015
- *Microcaecilia marvaleewakeae* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2013
- *Microcaecilia rochai* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2011
- *Microcaecilia supernumeraria* Taylor, 1969
- *Microcaecilia taylori* Nussbaum & Hoogmoed, 1979
- *Microcaecilia trombetas* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2011
- *Mimosiphonops reinhardti* Wilkinson & Nussbaum, 1992
- *Mimosiphonops vermiculatus* Taylor, 1968
- *Siphonops annulatus* (Mikan, 1822)
- *Siphonops hardyi* Boulenger, 1888
- *Siphonops leucoderus* Taylor, 1968
- *Siphonops paulensis* Boettger, 1892

Typhlonectidae (5/13)

- *Atretochoana eiselti* (Taylor, 1968)
- *Chthonerpeton arii* Cascon & Lima-Verde, 1994
- *Chthonerpeton braestrupi* Taylor, 1968
- *Chthonerpeton exile* Nussbaum & Wilkinson, 1987
- *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)
- *Chthonerpeton markwilkinsoni* Santos, Pineschi & Zaher, 2025
- *Chthonerpeton noctinectes* Silva, Britto-Pereira & Caramaschi, 2003
- *Chthonerpeton perissodus* Nussbaum & Wilkinson 1987
- *Chthonerpeton tremembe* Maciel, Leite, Silva-Leite, Leite & Cascon, 2015
- *Chthonerpeton viviparum* Parker & Wettstein, 1929
- *Nectocaecilia petersii* (Boulenger, 1882)
- *Potomotyphlus kaupii* (Berthold, 1859)
- *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)

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Figure 3. Species described since the list published by Segalla et al. (2021): (a) *Phantasmarana tamuia*, (b) *Physalaemus araxa*, (c) *Pseudopaludicola chimaera*, (d) *Pseudopaludicola javae*, (e) *Adenomera guarani*, (f) *Rupirana kaatinga*, (g) *Odontophrynus reigi*, (h) *Odontophrynus toledo*, (i) *Proceratophrys korekore*, (j) *Proceratophrys velhochico*. Photos by: L Malagoli (a); LF Toledo (b); LA Silva (c, d, i); DJ Santana (e, g); S Mângia (f); MT Moroti (h); DG Cavalheri (j).

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